

‘/fO6/afh’] syfsf] k|hfltk/s cWoog

s[iOfk|;fb ;']bL

k|fWofks, efiff ;flxTo ljefu, zxLb :d[lt ax'd'vL SofDk;, /Tggu/, lrtjg

n]v;/

k|:t't cfn]vdf syfsf/ ljZj]/k|;fb sf]O/fnfsf] ...'/fO6/afh]' syfsf] k|hfltk/s cWoog ul/Psf] 5 . ;flxTosf ;dfhzf:qL 6]gsf k|hfltk, lfOf / kl/]z dfGotfdWo] k|:t't cfn]vdf ...'/fO6/afh]' syfdf k|hfltk/s dfGotf cGtu{t k|hfltk klxrf, k|hfltk ;DaGw / k|hfltk k|efjsf cj:yfxçsf] vf]hL u/L ljZn]ifOf ug]{ p2]Zo /flvPsf] 5 . o;df syfsf] ljZn]ifOf ubf{ 6]gsf k|hfltk dfGotfnfO{ d'Vo cfwf/ agfOPsf] 5 . ‘.../fO6/afh]' syfdf k|hfltk/s cj:yfxçsf] vf]lh ug]{ qmddf k|hfltk klxrf, k|hfltk ;DaGw / k|hfltk k|efj pkzLif{s lbP/ ljZn]ifOf ul/Psf] 5 . o; ljZn]ifOfdf ‘.../fO6/afh]' syfsf d'Vo rl/q /fO6/afh] / ef]l6gLdf cfo{ / dª\uf]n k|hfltk klxrfgsf] k'li6 ePsf] b]vfOPsf] 5 eg] cGthf{tLo ;DaGw / k|efjaf6 ljsl;t dfg];s tyf zf/Ll/s ;dk{Ofaf6 k|fKt x'g] ;Gt'li6df k|]dsf] pRr cfb{z :jçk k|fKt x'g] lgisif{ lgsflnPsf] 5 . sf]O/fnfsf syfdf k|hfltk/s cWoog Tolt gePsf] kl/l:yltdf 6]gsf] k|hfltk dfGotfsf cf8df of] cfn]vg ul/Psf] ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qLo dfGotfsf s;Ldf sf]O/fnfsf syfsf] cWoog / ljZn]ifOf ug{ rfxg] hf] s;}nfO{ of] cfn]v pkof]uL aGg ;Sg] ck]lff ul/Psf] 5 .

d'Vo zAbfjnL M ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:q, k|hfltk, d"n cfbz{sf lRgx, k|hfltk klxrf, k|hfltk ;DaGw

. cWoogsf] kl/ro

ljZj]Zj/k|;fb sf]O/fnf -lj=;+= !(&!-@)#(_ g]kfnL ;flxTosf k|l;4 cfVofgsf/ x'g\ . sf]O/fnfn] ljz]if u/L pkGof;; syf / cfTdj[tfGt n]vgsf lf]qdf snd rnfPsf 5g\ . pgsf tLg 3'DtL -lj=;+= @)@%_ g/]Gb| bfO -lj=;+= @)@&_ ;'lDgdf -lj=;+= @)@&_ df]lbcfOg -lj=;+= @)#^_ lx6n/ / ox'bL -lj=;+= @)@)_ / afa' cdf / 5f]/f -lj=;+= @)@)_ 5 j6f pkGof; k|sflzt ePsf 5g\ . To:t} pgsf] Pp6f b]lgsL h]nhg{n -lj=;+= @)@)_ sf çkdf k|sflzt 5 eg] d]/f] hLjg syf -lj=;+= @)!!_ cfm\gf] syf -lj=;+= @)@)_ / cfTdj[QfGt -lj=;+= @)%%_ klg k|sflzt 5g\ . syfsf/ sf]O/fnfsf] syfofqf eg] lxGbL efiffsf] syfn]vgaf6 k|f/De ePsf] dflgG5 . xl/k|;fb zdf{ -@)^&M#@_ sf cg';f/ sf]O/fnfn] !(*& b]lv syf-n]vg k|f/De u]/sf x'g\ / Tof] syf n]vg lxGbL efiffsf] ...'jx' -!(*&_ syfaf6 g] k|f/De ePsf] lyof] . pgsf] g]kfnL efiffsf] klxnf] syf ...'rGb|jbg' xf] h'g zf/bf -lj=;+= !((@_ klqsdf k|sflzt ePsf] lyof] . o:t} ;"o{ljqmd 1jfnLsf] ;Dkfbgdf bflh{lnªaf6 k|sflzt syfs';d -lj=;+= !((%_ df ...'zq', ...'ljxf' / '...l;kfxL' syf k|sflzt ePsf 5g\ . k':tssf çkdf pgsf bf]ifl rZdf -lj=;+= @))^_ / Zj]te]/jL -lj=;+= @)#(_ syf ;+u|xxç g]kfnL syf Oltxf;d} dxœjk"Of{ s[lt x'g\ . bf]ifl rZdfdf pgsf

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;f|x|j6f syf ;°Int 5g\ eg] Zj]te)/jLdf hDdf rf/j6f syfxç ;°Int 5g\ . cGo ...'rGb|jbg' -zf/bf !((^_ ...'åGåk|]d' -zf/bf !((&_ / ...dx/fhsf] 'j/L' -o'ujf0fL @))%_ syfxç km'6s/ kqklqsfdf k|sflzt eP klg kl5 ;a} syfxç xl/k|;fb zdfå{f/f ;Dkflbt ljZj]Zj/k|;fb sf]O/fnfsf syf -@)^&_ df ;°Int 5g\ . o;/L sf]O/fnfsf hDdf 5AaL;j6f g]kfnL syfxç k|sflzt ePsf 5g\ . sf]O/fnfsf syfxçsf] cg]s sf]Ofaf6 k7g / cWoog ug{ ;lsG5 . pgsf syfxç ;dfhzf:qLo b[li6sf]Ofaf6 klg ljZn]if0fLo 5g\ .

;flxTolagfsf] ;dfh x'g;S5 t/ ;dfhlagfsf] ;flxTo x'g ;Sb}g . ;flxTodf ;dfhsf hftLo çk, eflifs cj:yf, wfld{s k|rng, ;fF:s[lts k/Dk/f, k|fs[lts tyf ;fdflhs kof{j/Of, /fhg}lts cj:yf / cfly{s cj:yfsf 9fFrF cflb cfj:yf / çkxçsf] k|:t'lt x'g] ePsf] ;flxTo / ;dfhsf] cGt;{DaGw 5 . ;dfhaf6 ;flxTosf] hGd x'g] / ;flxTodf ;dfhsf] k|ltaDa emNsg] ePsf] ;flxTo / ;dfh cGtlge{/ klg 5g\ . ;flxTodf ;dfhzf:q;Fu ;DalGwt ljfonfO{ hf]8]/ ul/g] j}1flgs cWoog k4lt g} ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:q xf]kl5Nnf] ;o jif{df ;+:s[ltsf] ef]ltsjfbL JofVofsf cfwf/df snfxçsf] h'g ;dfhzf:q ljsl;e Psf] 5, To;sf] Ps çk ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:q xf] -kf08]o, ;g\ !(* (M%_ . ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qn] ;flxTodf ;flxTos k|lqmofsf] cWoog ub{5 .

;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qLo lrGtgnfO{ cfw'lgs ;dfhdf ;flxTosf] ;Qf / ;fy{stfsf] kl/ro;Fu} k|fb'ef{j ePsf] af]l4s k|oTgsf çkdf lnOG5;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:q ca ;dfhzf:qeGbf km/s Ps ;flxTo ljwfsf çkdf ljsl;t x'Fb} 5 -kf08]o, ;g\ !(* (M#@_ . ;flxTonfO{ ;flo gdf]gsg u/]sf] ;fdflhs hLjgsf] cWoog ca k"Of{ x'g ;Sb}g . ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qdf ;dfh;Fu ;flxTosf/sf] ;DaGw, p;sf] ;fdflhs l:ylt / p;n] k|:t't u/]sf] ;fdflhs ;+;f/sf] cWoog x'G5 . ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qn] Jofks ;fdflhs k|lqmof cGtu{t lqmofzLn ;Dk"Of{ ;flxTo k|lqmofsf] ljleGg ult / kl/Of]ltxçsf] JofVof ub}{ ;flxTosf] jf:tljs ;fdflhs ;jçksf] kl/ro u/fpF5 / To;df ;fwf/Of kf7ssf] klg cle?lr hufpg ;xof]u k'¥ofpF5 . ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qLo lrGtgsf] k|f/De ;dfh;Fu ;flxTosf] vf]hL;Fu} ePsf] dflgPsf] 5 . o;} ;Gbe{df k|:t't cWoogdf ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qsf] ljfs;df dxÇEjk"Of{ e"lidsf v]Ng] 6]gsf] k|hfltk/s dfGotfsf cfwf/df ljZj]Zj/k|;fb sf]O/fnfsf] ...'/fO6/afh]' syfsf] cWoog ul/Psf] 5 .

cWoogsf] ;d:of / p2]Zo

;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:q Ps :yflkt dfGotf xf] . o; dfGotfleq 6]gsf] k|hfltt cWoog klg cWoogsf] Pp6f d'Vo cfwf/ xf] . 6]gsf k|hfltt dfGotfsf cfwf/df ljZj]Zj/k|fb sf]O/fnfsf] ...'/fO6/afh]' syfsf] klg cWoog ug{ ;lsG5 eGg] ljfonfO{ d'Vo ;d:of agfP/ k|:t't cWoog ul/Psf] 5 . o; cWoogsf] p2]Zo ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qsf] ljfs;df dxÇEjk"Of{ e"lidsf v]Ng] lxKkf] nfO6 c8f]N8 6]gsf] k|hfltt, lf0f / kl/]z dfGotfdWo] k|hfltt dfGotfsf cfwf/df ljZj]Zj/k|;fb sf]O/fnfsf] ...'/fO6/afh]' syfsf] cWoog ug'{ /x]sf] 5 . o; d"n p2]Zo;Fu ;Da4 eP/ cfp]g] cGo p2]Zoxç lgDglnlvt 5g\ M

- s_ syfsf/ sf]O/fnfsf] /fO6/afh] syfsf] k|hfltt klxrfgsf cj:yfxçnfO{ b]vfp]g',
- v_ syfsf/ sf]O/fnfsf] /fO6/afh] syfsf] k|hfltt ;DaGwnfO{ b]vfp]g',
- u_ syfsf/ sf]O/fnfsf] /fO6/afh] syfsf] k|hfltt k|efjsf cj:yfxçnfO{ b]vfp]g' .

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k|:t't cWoog ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qLo cWoog k4ltleqsf] k|hflttut dfGotfdf s]lGb|t /x]sf] 5 . k|hflttut cWoogsf ;}4flGts dfGotfsf cf8df /x]/ lJzn]ifOf ul/Psfn] o; cWoogdf cfudgfTds ljlwsf] k|of]u ul/Psf] 5 . g]kfnL ;dfnf]rgfsf lf]qdf k|hfltk/s cWoog Tolt k'/fgf] dfGotf gePsfn] st} st} lgudgfTds ljlw klg cfPsf] 5 . syfsf] ljj]rgfsf qmddf jOf{gfTds tyf JofVofTds ljlwsf] klg k|of]u ePsf] 5 eg] k|hfltk/s ;}4flGts dfGotfsf cf8df k|hflttut klxrfg, k|hflttut ;DaGw / k|hflttut k|efjsf cfwf/df syfsf/ lJzj]Zj/k|;fb sf]O/fnfsf] ...'/fO6/afh]' syfsf] k|hfltk/s cWoog ul/Psf] 5 .

6]g / k|hfltk/s dfGotf k|mfG;]nL lJrf/s lxKkf]nfO6 c8f]nkm 6]g -;g\ !*@*~!*(#_ ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qsf k|jt{s g} dflgG5g\ . 6]gsf ;flxTo / snf;DaGwL dfGotfsf] k|efj kl5Nnf ;flxTo lRgtsxçdf k/]sf] 5 . pgsf c+u|]hL ;flxTosf] Oltxf;, snfsf] bz{g / O6fnLsf] ofqf h:tf k':tssf snf;DaGwL n]vdf ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qLo wf/Off JoQm ePsf 5g\ . 6]gn] c+u|]hL ;flxTodf dfq xf]Og k|mfG;]nL ;flxTodf klg n]v]sf 5g\ . pgn] cfkm\gf ;dsfnLg /]l;g / afNhfS cflbsf lgaGwsf] klg cfnf]rgf u/] . lxGbL ;dfnf]rs d]g]h/ kf08]o -;g\ !(! M !@!_ sf cg';f/

Oltxf;sf/ 6]gsf x/]s cfnf]rgfdf ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qLo b[li6sf]Of cfPsf] 5 . ;flxTosf ;dfhzf:qL 6]g ;flxTonfO{ ;fdflhs r]tgfsf] pTkfbg dfGb5g\ . pgsf] ;dfhzf:qLo k4lt ;flxTos s[ltaf6 r]tgf -n]vs_ tkm{ / r]tgf6 r]tgf]gd{Ofsf] kl/l:ylttkm{ a9]sf] 5 . pgn] r]tgf]gd{Ofsf] kl/l:ylt ljj]rg ug]{ qmddf k|hfltt, lfOf tyf kl/]Zfsf] cGtlqmfaf6 r]tgfsf] lgd{Of x'g] atfPsf 5g\ / ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qLo dfGotfsf çkdf k|hfltt, lfOf tyf kl/]z l;4fGt cufl8 ;f/]sf 5g\ .

;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qdf k|hfltk/s cjwf/Off 6]gsf] b]g xf] . 6]g j:t'jfbL b[li6sf]Of /fVg] ;dfhzf:qL x'g\ . pgn] ...snf h'g dfgl;stf6 pTkGg x'G5, Tof] dfgl;stf s;/L tof/ x'G5 < eGg] k|Zgsf] pQ/df k|hfltt, o'u tyf kl/]z l;4fGt cufl8 NofPsf 5g\ -kf08]o, ;g\ !*(M !@\$_ . 6]gsf dtdf ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qLo cWoogstf{n] ;flxTodf JoQm ePsf] k|hfltsf ljifodf cWoog ug{'k5{ lsgeg] ;flxTosf/n] cfkm\gf] l;h{gfsf] ;fdu|L cfkm\gf] ;dfhsf] k|hflttaf6 lnPsf] x'G56]gn] k|hflttfO{ j+zfg'ut u'Of, zf/Ll/s jgfj6 tyf hfthfltsf k|ltef, ;jefj, lJz]iftf Pjd\ kf/Dkl/s dfgl;stfs çkdf kl/eflft u/]sf 5g\ . -l;ªp8, ;g\ !(&@, pb\w[t, lf]qL, @)^\$M@!_ . 6]gsf cg';f/ ...;flxTosf] cWoogaf6 To;sf] /rgfsfnf dflg;xçdf kfOg] efjgxfçsf] çk, lJrf/sf] ult / hLjgsf cj:yfxçsf] af]w x'G5 . -kf08]o, ;g\ !*(M !!*_ . ;dfh ljleGg k|hflttçsf] ;d"x xf] . ;flxTo ;fdflhs pTkfbg ePsfn] To;df ljleGg k|hflttçsf] k|efj /xG5 . pgLxçsf] cfrf/ lJrf/ / Jojxf/af6 g} ;flxTosf] hGd x'G5 . To;]n] ;flxTodf k|hfltk/s cWoogsf] dxœj /x]sf] 5 .

6]gn] k|hfltt cGtu{t JolQmsf] ;xh tyf j+zfg'ut lJz]iftf, dfgl;s agfj6 / zf/Ll/s ;+rgf cflbsf] rrf{ u/]sf 5g\ . Ps} k|hfltt klg b]zsfnsf sf/Of 6f9f 6f9f k'u]kl5 ToxfFsf] xfj kfgL df6f] cg';f/ s]xL ablnb} hfG5 eg] pgLxçdf j+zfg'ut ;dfgtf klg ljBdfg /xG5 . lgd{nf h}g -;g\ !((@M @@_ n] 6]gsf] k|hfltt dfGotfsf] JofVof ub}{ dfgjhflttç b]zsfnsf kl/l:yltn] leGg-leGg kl/l:yltdf /x] klg d"n cfbz{sf lRgxxç ljBdfg /xg] s'/f JoQm u/]sL 5g\ . s'g} k|hfltsf rl/qut lJz]iftfç hnjo', df6f] tyf Oltxf;sf

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dxfg\ 36gfczsf pkh x'G5g\ . 6]gn] k|mfG;df df]Gtg, OUn}08df z]S;lko/ / hd{gLdf u]6]n] k|ltek"Of{ ;flxTo l;h{gf ug{'nfO{ klg k|hfltk/s ljz]iftf dfg]sf 5g\ . pgLxç;Fu /x]sf] ljzi6 ;f}Gbof{g'e"lt / l;h{gf ug{ ;Sg] lfdtf k|hfltk/s ljz]iftf xf]6]gsf dtdf k|ltek Pp6f zlQm xf] . k|ltek zlQmsf] ljsf; b]zsf n / jftfj/Of cg';f/ x'G5 / To;nfO{ cflh{t lziff / P]ltxfl;s 36gfn] yk zlQm k|bfg ub{5 -kf08]o, ;g\ !(* (M!@%_ . o;af6 6]gn] JolQmk|ltek / jftfj/OfnfO{ dxTj lbPsf] :ki6 x'G5 .

6]gsf] k|hfltklxrfgsf] cfwf/ k|hfltsf] zf/LI/s ;+/rgf klg xf] . s'g} k|hfltk cUnf s'g} xfrf x'G5g\ eg] st} uf]/f st} sfnf x'G5g\ . d+uf]Inog / cfo{xç Ps} hfltk eP klg pgLxçsf] zf/LI/s ;+/rgfdf s]xL k|hfltk/s leGg ljz]iftfç kfOG5g\6]gn] o; lsl;dsf] k|hfltk/s wf/Ofsf] JofVofsf nflu cfm\gf ;dsfnLg ljsf;jfbL 8flj]gsf] lrgtgaf6 klg d2t lnPsf 5g\ -kf08]o, ;g\ !(* (M!@%_ . 8flj]gn] b]zsf n cg';f/sf] df6f] kfgLsf sf/Ofn] k|s[ltsf kl/l:yltxç;Fu ;fdgf ug{;Sg] lfdtf s'g} k|hfltk a9\b} hfG5 / pgLxçdf s'g} ljz]iftf yk 36 x'Fb} hfG5 eg]sf 5g\ . pgsf cg';f/ To;af6 pTkGg x'g] cnu–cnu ljz]iftsf sf/Ofn] cnu–cnu k|hfltkç aGb} hfG5g\ / pgLxçsf] zf/LI/s ;+/rgf ablnb} hfG5 . o;/L 6]gn] ;flxTo ;fdflhs pTkfbg / ;fdflhstf ljleGg k|hfltkçsf] klxrfg ;d"x ePsf] ;flxToaf6 k|hfltk/s klxrfgxç x'g ;Sg] eGb} ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qLo cWoogsf lglDt k|hfltknfO{ d'Vo ljifosf çkdf lnPsf 5g\ .

/fO6/afh] syfsf] k|hfltk/s cWoog

ljz]jzj/k|;fb sf]O/fnfsf] .../fO6/afh] syf Zj]te}/jL syf;+u|x -lj=;+= @)#(_ df ;a\slnt 5 . k|:t't syf k|hfltk/s klxrfg ePsf] syf xf] . o; syfnfO{ 6]gsf] k|hfltk/s dfGotfsf cfwf/df cWoog ug{ ;lsG5 . o; qmddf k|:t't syfnfO{ k|hfltk/s cWoogcGtu{t k|hfltk klxrfg, k|hfltk k|efj / k|hfltk ;DaGwsf b[li6n] cWoog ul/Psf] 5 .

k|hfltk klxrfg

syfsf d'Vo kfq /fO6/afh] / ef]6]gL b'a} k|hfltk klxrfg x'g] u/L gfds/Of ul/Psf kfq x'g\ . /fO6/afh] cfo{ a|fÅd0f hfltsf x'g\ eg] ef]l6gL dª\uf]n ef]6] hfltsL x'g\ eGg] s'/f syfsf/n] o;/L klxrfg u/fPsf 5g\ M lgd'sf a|fÅd0fn] d]/f] vfg]–lkpg], n'ufkmf6f / c? ;fgf–;fgf ;'ljwfsf s'/fdf Wofg lbPsf] b]Vbf d ;xh} pgL;Fu x]nd]n ug{ yfn]+ . -k[= !(_

==== Pp6L ef]l6gL aflnsfnfO{ tLg gDa/ kxf8af6 hfL/ vfg ;x/df cfPsf /fO6/afh]n] Ps lbg c8\8faf6 kmIs{bf bof u]/ cf>o lbFb} cfm\gf] 3/df gNofPsf] eP ;fob To;n] k|]d g} kfp] yL, g s'i7/f]u g} . -k[= !*_

'ef]l6gL ...d' sf] cleJolQmdf k|:t't ePsf] .../fO6/afh] syfsf oL ;floxçn] /fO6/afh] / ef]l6gLsf] k|hfltk klxrfgnfO{ k|:6 kf]/sf 5g\ . 6]gn] dfgj k|hfltkç b]zsfnsf kl/l:ylt] leGg leGg kl/l:yltf /x] klg d"n cfbz{sf lrgxxç ljBdfg x'g] s'/f cf]+NofPsf 5g\ . o; syfdf klg cfo{ a|fÅd0f k|hfltsf JolQmxç k'/]t, kl08t / c8\8f cbfnfsf] hfL/ tyf n]vgbf; cflb e"lidsdf x'g', wd{ sd{df rfv lng', / O{Zj/Lo ;Qdf ljzj; ug{' pgLxxçsf] d"n cfbz{sf] klxrfg xf] . To; u/L syfsL gflosf ef]6]gLdf klg

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j+zfg'ut nlf0fxç kfOG5g\ . p;n] cfkm" / /fO6/afh]sf] cGthf{tLo ;DaGwnfO{ ...of] s] x'g nflu/x]5 < s] of] x'g] s'/f xf] < s] o;df c:jflestf 5}g < ck|f;ª\lustf < km]l/ a |fXd0f k'?if / ef]l6gL gf/Lsf] j]jflxs ;DaGw ;fdflhs b[li6df a]d]n s'/f xf]Og / < -k[= @_ eg]/ c:jefljs 7fg]sf] b]lvG5 . ef]l6gLn] a|fXd0f /fO6/afh] / cfkm" ef]l6gLaLrsf] d]nldnfk, cfsif{Of / cGtª\u cflTds k|]d clg j]jflxs ;DaGwnfO{ ;d]t c:jefljs ta/n] x]g{' p;sf] j+zfg'ut u'Of xf] . hftLo e]befjsf b[li6n] x]g]{ Toltv]/sf] xfd|f] ;dfhdf o; lsl;dsf] ;DaGwnfO{ p;n] a]d]n 7fg]sL 5 . To;} eP/ xf]nf ...d kfq ef]l6gLn] ...d]/f] To;} lbg :jo+j/ ePsf] eGg] uDeL/ cg'ej x'FbfX'Fb] klq kTgLsf] cf;gdf plSng vf]Hbf dnfO{ láljwf eO/Xof] . -k[= @_ eg]/ láljwf l:y]tsf] cfTdsyg u/]sL 5 . xfd|f] ;dfhdf cfTdLo ;DaGw hlt uf9f eP klq j]jflxs ;DaGwn] dfq ;dflhs dfGotf kfp]g] ePsf]n] To]f] cf;gdf a:g p;sf] dg láljwdf k]/sf] b]lvG5 . dfgl;s ;DaGw alnof] x'FbfX'Fb] klq a|fXd0f / ef]l6gLaLrsf] j]jflxs ;DaGw sdhf]/ 7fGg' kg]{ cj:yf p;sf] cGtª\udf ljBdfg j+zfg'ut ;f]r xf], h'g ef]l6gLsf] k|hftLo klxrfgsf] cfwf/ ag]sf] 5 . k|:t't syfdf ef]l6gLsf h]7L, dflxnL / ;flxFnf] lbbLxçsf] ;f]r, pgLxçsf] hLjgk|ltsf] b[li6sf]Of / pgLxçn] b]vfPsf] :jhftLo ;+:sf/k|ltsf] ;r]tgfn] d+uf]n ef]6]hfltdf kfOg] cj:yfxçsf] af]w x'G5 . ;a] k'?ifnfO{ Ps] gh/n] x]g]{ p;sf lbbLxç hLjgdf /dfOnf] ug{'k5 / wg sdfpg'k5{ eGg] b[li6sf]Of o;/L /fVb5g\ M

...Pp6f afx'g /fO6/ / csf]{ vqL sKtfg of /f0ff hg]{n csf]{ g]jf/ ;/bf/ ;a] k'?if Ps] x'g\ . pgLxç of] eŞLdf kfn];Fu cfP/ d;Fu /dfOnf] u]/ uPsf 5g\ . ;fFRg} So} km/s 5}g-a}gL, So} km/s 5}g . -k[= @@_ syfsf/ sf]O/fnfn] o; syfdf dg ldN5 / dfgl;s ;Gt'li6 k|fKt x'G5 eg] c? hftkft, wd{-;+:s[lt s]xL klq 5]saf/ aGg ;Sb}g eGg] j]rfl/s dt lbPsf 5g\ . 6]gsf] k|hfltk/s lrGtg, ltgsf ljzi6tf, w]/) ;dokl5 Pscsf]{ k|hfltdf kg]{ k|efj / k|hfltxç hlt 6f9f6f9f k'u] klq k|hfltk/s d"n cfbz[sf] c+z affsL /xg] dfGotf o; syfdf klq b]lvG5 . ef]l6gLn] j]Zofj[IQ k];f ;xh} cFufNg;Sg'df k|hfltk/s d"n cfbz{s] cjz]if xf] . o;/L k|:t't syfdf /fO6/afh], ef]l6gL / p;sf lbbLxçsf] e"ldsf, kfqxçsf] gfdS/Of cflb klfn] k|hflttut klxrfg ePsf] 5 . k|hflttut ;DaGw

/fO6/afh] syfsf] k|hflttut ;DaGw cfo{ k'?if / d+uf]n gf/Lsf] dfgl;s / b]lxs ;DaGwdf ljsl;t ag]sf] 5 . leGg k|hfltsf k'?if / gf/L larsf] b]lxs /Qm;DaGwnfO{ k|]dsf] pRr bhf{ lbOPsf] 5 . ;fdflhs b[li6sf]Ofn] k|hflttut a]d]n ;DaGw :jLsfo{ gxf]nf t/ syfsf/n] :jLsf]/sf 5g\ / df]g :jLs[lt klq lbPsf 5g\ . 'syfsL ...d' kfq ef]l6gLn] k'?if / gf/Lsf] ;DaGwnfO{ o;/L x]/]sL 5 M

...clUgsf cufl8sf] dGqkf7 of s'g] ?vd'lg ePsf] dfNofbfg-k|bfg, of r"Xnf]sf] tLg]6f kTy/sf] k"hf-cr{gf-k'?if-gf/Lsf] cfGtl/s ;DaGwsf] k|s6Ls/Of xf]Og / - Ps k|sf/sf] 3f]if0ff < d'Vo ljifo s] xf] < k'?if / gf/Lsf] tflŒjs ;DaGw jf To;sf] 3f]if0ff < k|f0f of z/L/

< -k[= @_ eg]l6gLsf larf/df xfd|f] lj]fx k4lt k'?if / gf/Lsf] ;DaGwsf] 3f]if0ff dfq xf] . o:tf] k|yfn] b]lxs ;DaGw lj:tf/ ug{ ;S5 t/ dfgl;s ;DaGw cw'}/ /xg] b]lvG5 . ef]l6gLn] ;fdflhs :jLs[ltsf] cf]krfl/stf / j]wflgstfeGbf dfly p7]/ kTgLsf] :yfg u|x0f u/]sL 5 . pm b]lxs / dfgl;s çkdf

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/fO6/afh]k|lt ;dlk{t ePsl 5 / o;af6 pm k"Of{ ;Gt'li6sf txdf k'u]sL 5 . ;fdflhs dof{bfsf sf/Ofn] dgdf cg]sf]+ lâl]wfsf cj:yfxç hGdbf hGdb} klg cfo{ /fO6/afh]sf] cg'u|x / k|]ddf pm lglN{Kt / ;dlk{t ag]sL 5 . p;n] kTgLTj / dft[Tjsf] ;'vnfO{ o;/L JoQm u/]sL 5M

...kTgLTj / dft[Tjsf] ;'v-|k|of / dftf x'g] efUo Û dnfO{ nfUof], d b]jLb]jtfsf] ;dslfdf 5' . cgGt 5, d]/f] ;'v / ;Gtf]if . 7'nf] efUo lnP/ cfPsf] 5' . -k[= @@_ k|:t't syfdf k|hftut ;DaGwlj:tf/n] kTgLTj / dft[Tjdfq xf]Og lkt[Tjsf] :yfg klg lbPsf] 5 . /fO6/afh]af6 k|fKt ;a} k|sf/sf ;'vaf6 ef]l6gLn] cfkm" b]jLb]jtfsf] ;dslfdf k'u]sf] cg'ej lnPsl 5 . To; k|sf/sf] ;'v p;nfO{ ;fob /fO6/afh]n] dfq lbg ;Sy] . To;} eP/ xf]nf p;n] .../fO6/afh] ð of] d]/f] hfaf] z/L/nfO{ ck}{/ klg ltdLnfo{ arfpF5' . -k[= @\$ _ eg]/ /fO6/afh]sf] pkrf/ u/fPsl 5 . oxF dg rf]vf] 5 eg] z/L/ h'l7b}g eGg] b[li6sf]0f e]l6G5 M

...dg l;;ª\ u eP/ z/L/n] dfq u/]sf] sfo{ s] To:tf] cfwf/ x'g ;S5, h;df kfk c8\g ;sf];\

ð dgsf] lgd{ntfdf g'xfP/ s] z/L/sf kfkfsf] df]rg x'Fb}g < j]Zofz/L/df kltj| tf k|f0f hLljt} /x'Fb}g / ð dnfO{ nfUYof], j]Zof;Hhdf ;'t]sf] z/L/ d]/f] xf]Og, d ToxF x'Gg . -k[= @\$ _ ef]l6gLsf nflu b}lxs / dfg];s ;'v km/s km/s x'g\ . dfg];s ;'vsf t'ngfdf b}lxs ;'v lfl0fs 5g\ . dgsf] lgd{ntfdf g'xfPsf] z/L/ slxNo} la6'nf] x'Fb}g . p;n] z/L/ a]r]/ klg /fO6/afh]sf] pkrf/ hlt ug{ ;sL To;df pm lgs} ;Gt'i6 ePsl 5 . p;n] eg]sL 5M æ...d]/f /fO6/afh] ð d]/f] ;fdYo{sf] r/d;Ldf;Dd k'u/ d]n] hlt ug{ ;Sy]+, u/]F z/L/ lbP/ klg . ;fgf] ;Gtf]if o;}df 5 .Æ -k[= @% _ . o;/L k|:t't syfdf kltsf] ;]jf / p;sf] k|f0f lxtsf nflu gf/Ln] x/]s sbd p7fpg ;S5] eGg] ef]l6gLsf] leGg k|hftLo ;DaGwsf cj:yaf6 p7]sf] pRr dgf]efj lgs} ;Ddfghgs b]lvG5 .

k|hftut k|efj

s'g} Ps k|hft csf]{ k|hftsf glhs cfP/ Ps csf{k|lt k|efljt x'g'nfO{ k|hftLo k|efj dflgG5 . 6]gn] Ps} k|hft klg b]zsfnsf sf/Of 6f9f-6f9f k'u]k15 ToxFsf] xjff, kfgL / df6f] cg';f/ s]xL ablnb} hfg] / Ps k|hft csf]{ k|hftaf6 k|efljt x'g] s'/f cf]+NofPsf 5g\/fO6/afh] syfsf /fO6/afh] / ef]l6gLn] Ps csf{sf] k|hftLo k|efjnfO{ :jLsf]/sf 5g\ . x]nDa'sL ef]6]gLnfo{ sf7df8f}+df dfUb} u/]sf] cj:yfdf /fO6/afh]n] 3/df NofPsf 5g\ / la:tf/} kTgLTjsf] bhf{ lbPsf 5g\ . d+uf]n ef]l6gL / cfo{ a|fXd0f /fO6/afh]sf] cyfx k|]d / b}lxs ;DaGwnfo{ syfn] dfGotf lbPsf] 5 . cfo{ a|fÅd0fsf] ;ª\utn] p;sf lrGtg / Jojxf/df klg kl/jt{g cfPsf

5g\ . k|:t't syfdf ef]l6gLsf ...d Pp6L u|fdL0f ef]6]gL aflnsf, clzlft, s]xL ghfGg] . d]n] :qL rf]nf lnP/ hGd]+

/z/L/wd{cg';f/ x'ls{b} uPF . -k[=!(_ egfOaf6 p;sf] cj:yf af]w ePsf] 5 . p;df cfo{ a|fXd0fsf] ;ª\ut / k|efjn] :qLTj, kltwd{ / z/L/wd{ cflbsf] :ki6 1fg klg ePsf] b]lvG5 . pm k|hftsf b[li6n] ef]l6gL eg]/ lrlgPsl eP klg /fO6/afh]sf k|efjn] Jojxf/ / cfrf/Ofdf a|fÅd0fL h:tL ag]sL 5 . /fO6/afh] a|fXd0f ePsn] pgdf a|fXd0f kl/jf/sf] ;+sf/ b]lvG5 . pgL O{Zj/Lo ;Qdf l]Zjf; /fV5g\ / ef]6]gLnfo{ klg Tof] ;+sf/ lbG5g\ . /fO6/afh]sf k|efjn] ef]l6gLn] O{Zj/, :ju{ / g/ssf] l]Zjf; ug{

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nfu]sf] s'/f syfdf o;/L b]vfOPsf] 5 M æ.../fO6/afh]n] eGg'x'GYof]- O{Zj/ 5g\ / eGg'x'GYof]- kfk-k'0o klg 5, lsgg] O{Zj/ 5 -k[= !&_ .Æ o; sygaf6 Psflt/ /fO6/afh]df a |fXd0fxçn] O{Zj/nfO{ dfGg] j+zfg'ut u'0f b]lvPsf] 5 eg] csf{lt/ a |fXd0fsf] lgs6tf / u'0fn] ef]6]gLnfO{ k|efj kf/]sf] oyfy{tf klg k|:6 ePsf] 5 . alxgL] cfkm\gf] hfltut ljzi6tf Tofu]/ cfo{ a |fXd0faf6 k|efljt eP/ afx'gsf] em}+ rfnrng / Jojxf/ u/]sf] ef]l6gLsf lbbLxçnfO{ dg k/]sf] 5}g . p;sL h]7L lbbLn] ...a}gL, tF s;/L abln5;\, s] ef] tnfO{, /S;L-hfF8 gvfg] /, of] hf8f]df klg gg'xfO{ gx'g] /] tFnfO{ . xfdL ef]6]gLnfO{ cfkm\g} Jojxf/ 5, xfdLn] afx'gL x'g vf]h]/ x'G5 / < -k[= @!_ eg]sL 5 . h]7L lbbLsf cleJolQmn] cfo{hflt / dª\uf]n hfltsf /Ltl:ylt leGg x'g] oyfy{tf b]lvPsf] 5 eg] ef]l6gLdf k/]sf] cfo{hfltsf] k|efjnfO{ klg cleJol~ht u/]sf] 5 . dflxnL lbbLn] klg alxgLnfO{ cfkm\g} hftLo :jefjdf kms{g pTk|]l/t ub}{ eg]sL 5 M

...d;Fu} a;\, a}gL æ of] e\$Ldf sfd w]/} al9/x]sf] 5, u|fxs klg ylk}5g\ . xfdL lbbL- a}gL ldn]/ /f]huf/ a9fpFnf . d PSnL - of] PSnf] z/L/n] Eofpg g;Sg] eof] . === =s] ePsf] 5 tFnfO{ < Pp6f afx'gsf] tF s] s'/f u5]{;\ . oxF d;Fu a;\ eg]sf] . To:tf /fO6/afh] slt cfpF5g\ slt .

;w}+ ;f6f]km]/f] ug{ vf]lh;\ eg] klg kfpF5;\ . -k[= @!_

ef]l6gLsL ;flxFnL lbbL klg b/af/ of /xg;xg / ;DkGgtfdf /dfP/ a;]sL 5 . p;n] klg alxgLnfO{ cfkm"ht:t' x'g k|]l/t u5]{ / eG5] M

...æoxLF cfoh, tF klg b/af/ k;\ . x]/\ === hfaf] Pp6f a |fXd0fsf] s'/f gu/\ . tF /fd|L 5;\, oxF b/af/df l5\$} cfkm\gf] 7fpF agfpg ;S5];\ . d g} oxF k/]sf] slt eof] / , /fgL eP/ a;]sL 5' .

/fhs'df/ oxF y'k|f 5g\=== hfaf] afx'g=====s] ePsf] 5 tFnfO{ <Æ -k[= @!_ ef]l6gL h'g lbbL;Fu ;Nnfx lng uP klg ;a}n] Pp6} lsl;dsf] ;Nnfx lbPsf 5g\ . cfkm\gf] hflt wd{sf] /Ltl:ylt cg';f/ h;/L ;'vef]u ug{ ;lsG5, To;/L hLjg lhpg'k5{ eg]/ lbbLxçn] ;Nnfx lbPsf 5g\ . ef]l6gLsf nflu k|]d dfgl;s pRr cfbz{sf] ;dk{Of xf] eg] lbbLxçsf nflu k|]d s'g} klg k'?if;Fusf] ;'tFO dfq xf] . p;sL dflxnL lbbLn] ...s:tf] k|]d eg]sf] t]/f] , b'nfx vf]h]/ Tof];Fu /flt ;'Tg', ToxL t xf] lg k|]d eg]sf] . c? s] vf]H5];\ To;df < h'g k'?if klg Pp6} xf] . -k[= @!_ eg]sL klg 5 . lbbLxçsf k'?if x/]s lbsf nflu x/]s x'g;S5g\ eg] cfo{ ;+sf/af6 k|efljt alxgL Tof] hLjgaf6 dfly p7]sL 5 . alxgLsf ;f]rfOdf k'?ifsf] ;+;u{dfq k|]d xf]Og p;k|ltsf] pRr ;dk{Of klg xf] . p;n] cfo{k'?if /fO6/afh];Fu dfq} cg'alGwt eP/ afFRg rfx]sL 5 / To;df hLjgsf] clGtd ;'v / O{Zj/Lo cfgGb 7fg]sL 5 . ef]l6gLdflysf] lbbLxçsf] bjfj hftLo ;+sf/ af]s]sf] dfgl;stfsf] bafa xf] . lbbLxçsf] ;hftLo ;+sf/sf] jsfnt u/]sf 5g\ . h]7L lbbL rf/j6f kltsL kTgL xf] eg] dflxnL lbbL klg ;w}+ xfx / lxlxdf /dfpg] ;jefjsL 5 . e\$Lk;ndf a;} To:tf /fO6/afh] slt cfpF5g\ slt eg]/ lagf ;dfilhs qf; ax'klt :jLsf{ ;lsg] dfgl;stf JoQm ub]{5} . ;dfnf]rs uf}tdsf cg';f/ /fO6/ afh] syfdf cfo{ / dª\uf]n hfltsf] ;Gbe{ 5 . pgn] g]kfn]sf] lxdfnL z]kf{ hfltljz]ifdf k|rlnt ax'kltk|yfsf] ;Gbe{ /x]sf] pNn]v u/sf 5g\ . -uf]td, @)&)M#%(_ . To;f] eP/ xf]nf ef]6]gLsf lbbLxç dĚf]n hftLo :jefjdf ;lhn} 9Ng ;s]sf 5g\ eg]

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ef]l6gL a|fXd0fsf] ;a\ut cg';f/sf] ;+:sf/ / hLjgz}nLdf 9INsPsL 5 . pgLxç rfxG5g\ alxgL klg cfkm" lxF8]s} af6f]df lxF8f];\ / ;'vsf] lhGbuL afFrF];\ . 6]gsf] dfGotf cg';f/ ef]l6gLsf lbbLxçdf k|hftLo d"n cfbz{sf lRgxxç 5g\ / ;dfhdf e\$Lk;n yfk]/ ToxFsf] x/]s kl/l:yltaf6 /dfOnf] lng ;s]sf 5g\ . t/ ef]l6gL cfo{ a|fXd0fsf] ;+:u{ / k|efjn} lbbLxçeGbf leGg cfr/Ofdf k'u]sL 5 / p;df cfTd;Ddfg / uf}/jsf] cg'e"lt klg 5 .

;fdflhs l:yltcg';f/ k|To]s k|hftlxç Pscsf{af6 k|efljt x'G5g\ . o; syfdf cfo{ a|fXd0faf6 ef]l6GLdfq xf]Og ls d+uf]n ef]l6GLaf6 cfo{ a|fXd0f /fO6/afh] klg k|efljt ag]sf 5g\ . /fO6/afh]sxF cfP/ la:tf/–la:tf/ pgsf] u[x:yLsf] Pp6f cª\ u x'g k'u]sL ef]l6GLaf6 /fO6/afh] slt k|efljt lyP eGg] s'/f syfsf lgDg c+zxçn] k'li6 ub{5g\ .

...of] Ps srf}/f b"w vfg}k5{, /fO6/afh] æ gq hLp s;/L nfU5 < pgL s]xL gaf]nL d]/f] xftaf6 srf}/f lnP/ b"w lkpFy] . d pleP/ x]l//xGy]F . -k[= !(_

.../fO6/afh]n] klg ddflysf] cfkm\gf] lge{/tfsf] k'/f k|df0f lbP/ Ps lbg eg]– n n]pm, d]/f] dlxgfsf'] tna . / afs;sf] ;frF f] klg . ca tna cfpq] lalQs } ltd }| xftdf /flvlbG5 ' . -k[= !(_ pko'{Qm c+zaf6 s] a'lemG5 eg] oxXF cfo{ /fO6/afh] / d+uf]n ef]l6gL Ps csf{af6 lgs} k|efljt 5g\ . ef]l6GLn] /fO6/afh]sf] dg lht]sL 5 . /fO6/afh] lg/Lx ag]/ xf] jf ef]l6GLaf6 cf}lw k|efljt eP/ xf] ;a} tfnfrfaL ;'lDKP/ a;]sf 5g\ / dfgl;s, b}lxs / Jojxf]s ;a} kifaf6 ;dlk{t 5g\ . pgsf] ;dk{Ofdf k|hftLo k|efj b]lvG5 . o;/L k|:t't syfdf sf]O/fnfn] cfo{ a|fXd0f / d+uf]n ef]l6gL Ps csf{af6 k|efljt ag]sf] / To; ;DaGwaf6 cfb{z k|]dsf] ;çk emlNsPsf] b]vfPsf 5g\ . cGthf{tLo ;DaGwk|lt syfsf/n] ;fdflhs ;b\efj /fv]sf] :ki6 x'G5 . lgisif{

.../fO6/afh] syf sf]O/fnfsf] k|hftk/s klxrfg x'g] syf xf] . 6]gsf k|hftlut dfGotfdf s;Ldf /x]/ o; syfsf] cWoog ug{ ;lS5 . o; syfdf cfo{ a|fXd0fhflt / d+uf]n ef]l6]hfltsf] klxrfg ePs]f 5 . syfsf/n] /fO6/afh] / ef]l6GLsf dfWodaf6 k|hfltsf] klxrfg dfq u/fPsf 5}gg\ ls ;fdflhs b[li6sf]0faf6 a]d]n ;DaGw 7flgg] /fO6/afh] / ef]l6GLsf] ;DaGwnfO{ kTgLTj, dft[Tj / lkt[Tjsf] tx;Dd k'¥ofPsf 5g\ . xfd|f ;dfhsf cf}krfl/s j}jflxs k|yfxçn] aflx/L cfj/Ofsf] dfq sfd sfo{ u/]sf x'G5g\ . d]n ljfxn] ljsl;t u/]sf cj:yfxç b}lxs ;DaGwsf cfwf/ dfq x'g\ . a]d]n ljfxn] ;fdflhs dof{bf k|fKt ug{ c;xh xf]nf t/ dfgl;s / b}lxs ;dk{Ofsf nflu s'g} aGb]h x'Fb}g . o; syfsf d'Vo kfq /fO6/afh] / ef]l6gL Ps csf{af6 k|efljt eP/ dfgl;s tyf b}lxs / la:tf/} ;fdflhs ;DaGw :yflkt ug{ ;lfd klg 5g\ . syfsf/n] o; syfdf d'Vo kfqs dfWodaf6 hftkft, wd{–;:s[ltn] k'?if / gf/L leGg k|hfltsf eP klg ;DaGw lj:tf/df s'g} afwf gkg]{ b]vfPsf 5g\ eg] csf{lt/ ef]l6GLsf lbbLxçsf] e"lidsfaf6 6]gsf] k|hftlut lRgtg, ltgsf ljzi6tf, w]/} ;dokl5 Pscsf]{ k|hftdf kg]{ k|efj / k|hftlxç hlt 6f9f6f9f k'u] klg k|hftlut d"n cfbz{sf] c+z afFsL /xg] pNn]v klg u/]sf 5g\ . lfo/f]un] u|:t ePsf] kltsf] pkrf/sf nflu ef]l6GLn] j]Zofj[lQ k];f ;xh} cFufNg;Sg'df klg k|hftlut d"n cfbz{s} cz]if b]lvG5 . k|hftlut cWoogsf b[li6n] of] syf ljzi6 /x]sf] 5 . syfsf/ sf]O/fnfn] syf n]vgsf] ;fdu|L cfkm" afFr]sf] ;dfhsf] cfo{ / ef]l6] k|hfltaf6 lnPsf 5g\ . o; syfdf k|hftlut cfTdfs] dgf]lj1fg k|s6 ePsf] 5 . syfsf/n] cfo{ a|fXd0f / cgfo{ ef]l6GLaLr

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lahftLo b}lxs /Qm;DaGw b}vfp/ k|hflttut ;b\efj /fv]sf] / leGg k|hfltsf] ;DaGwk|lt :jLs[lt lbPsf]
:ki6 ePsf] 5 .

;Gbe{ ;fdu|L

cfrfo{, s'df/ -@)#&_ ljZj]Zj/k|;fb sf]O/fnfsf] JolQmTj / pgsf syf Pjd\ syfsf]/tfsf]
ljZn]if0f / d"Nof°g -zf]wkq_, g]kfnL s]Gb|Lo ljefu, lq=lj= . sf]O/fnf, ljZj]Zj/k|;fb -lj=;+=
@)^\$ _ Zj]te}/jL -kfFr]= k|=_ nlnTk'/M ;femf k|sfzg .

uf}td, nld0fk|;fb -lj=;+= @)#&#_ ...ljZj]Zj/k|;fb sf]O/fnfsf cfVofgdf ljhtLo /St;DaGw, e[s'6L
;Dkf= Invt kf08] sf7df8f}+ M e[s'6L Ps]8]lds klAns]zg .

5]qL, pbo -lj=;+= @)^\$ _ ;dfhzf:qLo b[li6df OGb|axfb'/ /fO{sf cfVofgsf] cWoog, g]kfnL
s]Gb|Lo ljefu, lq=lj= .

h}g, lgd{nf -;g\ !((@_ ;flxTosf ;dfhzf:qLo lrGtg -bf]= ;+=_ lbNnL M lxGbL dfWod sfof{Gjog
lgb}{zgfno, lbNnL ljZj]Bfno .

kf08]o, d]g]h/ -;g\ !(*(_ ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:qsL e"ldsf M r08Lu9 M xl/of0ff ;flxTo csfbdL .

l;+x, aRrg -;g\ @))&_ ;flxTosf ;dfhzf:q, OnfxjfbM nf]sef/tL k|sfzg .

;]j]bL, /fh]Gb| -lj=;+= @)^(_ ...Pn]g l:jªup8sf dfGotf / ;flxTosf] ;dfhzf:q, k|fl1s ;+;f/Ù ;Dkf=
gj/fh kf}8]n, sf7df8f}+ M h'un klAns];g k|f= ln= . zdf{, xl/k|;fb -lj=;+= @)^&_ ljZj]Zj/k|;fb
sf]O/fnfsf syf, -rf]yf] k|=_ nlnTk'/ M ;femf k|sfzg .

n3'syf;“u cGo ljwfk |ljwfsf ;DaGw / c;DaGw

nld0f cof{n

;xk|fWofks, efiff;flxTo ljefu, zxLb :d[lt ax'd'vL SofDk;, /Tggu/, lrtjg

n]v;/f/

k|:t't n]v ljleGg ljwf / k|ljwf;Fu n3'syfsf] ;DaGw c;DaGw ;DaGwL cWoogdf cfwfl/t 5 . o;
n]vdf cfVofgsf tLg k|ljwf pkGof;, syf / n3'syfsf] t'ngfTds cWoog ub}{ oL tLg j6} k|ljwfxç Ps
cfk;df ;dfg h:tf] nfu] klg oL :jtGq 5g] eGg] lgisif{ lgsflnPsf] 5 . o;sf cltl/Qm o;df r'6\lsnf,
d'Qms, nfdf sljtf, dxfsfJo, v08sfJo, gf6s, lgaGw cflb ljwf k|ljwf;Fu n3'syfsf] t'ngfTds cWoog
klg ul/Psf] 5 . n3'syfsf] s'g} ljwf jf k|ljwf;Fu lgs6, s'g};Fu lgs6td / s'g};Fu b"/jtL{ ;DaGw :yflkt
x'g ;Sg] cfwf/nfO{ o; cWoogdf s]nfOPsf] 5 . o:t} o;df n3'syf;Fu sljtf, lgaGw / gf6ssf]
cGt3'{ngsf] cj:yfnfO{ lbUbz{g ul/Psf] 5 . o;df d"ntM k':tsfno lj]wsf] pkof]u ePsf] 5 . j0f{gfTds

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/ ljZn]ifOffTds ljwfsf] ;d]t o;df k|of]u ul/Psf] 5 . o; cfn]vsf] d"ne"t pB]Zo n3'syf;Fu cGo ljwfk|ljwfsf] ;DaGw s]nfpFb] ;flxTodf n3'syfsf] :yfg lgwf{/Of ug'{ / n3'syfsf] n]vg lzNksf] af]w u/fpg' /x]sf] 5 . n3'syfsf] ljleGg ljwfk|ljwf;Fusf] ;DaGw c;DaGw af/] hfgsf/L lng rfxg]xčsf nflu of] cWoog pkof]uL x'g] ck]lff ul/Psf] 5 .

k|d'v zAbfjnL M ljwfk|ljwf, nife]bgsf] ;fwgf, wfl/nf] Jo^a\Uor]tgf, cGt3'{ng .

cWoogsf] kl/ro

hLjg / hut\s]f ljleGg cg'e"ltxčnfO{ ;'nlnt z]nLn] ;hfP/ JoQm ug]{ n]vg g] ;flxTo xf] h;df dfgj sNof0fnfO{ k|Tolf jf k/f]If čkdf :yflkt ul/Psf] x'G5 . sYo / n]Vo egL o;nfO{ 5'6\ofpg ;lsG5 . sYo ;flxTo eg]sf] nf]s ;flxTo g] xf] h'g ;dfhdf df]lvs :jčkdf afFr]sf] x'G5 . nf]suLt, nf]ssyf, nf]sufyf cflb sYo ;flxTo x'g\ . Inlvt ;flxTo n]Vo :jčkdf k|s6 x'G5 . syf, pkGof;, sljtf, gf6s cflb n]Vo ;flxTosf kf6f x'g\ .

hxF;Dd Inlvt ;flxTosf] s'/f 5, o;nfO{ ;|i6f ;flxTo / b|i6f ;flxTo egL 5'6\ofpg ;lsG5 . ;|i6f ;flxTo l;h{gfTds ;flxTo xf] eg] b|i6f ;flxTo ;dfnf]rgfTds ;flxTo xf] . ;|i6f ;flxTosf d"ntM \$ ljwf 5g\ – cfVofg, sljtf, gf6s / lgaGw . cfVofgsf pkGof;, syf / n3'syf u/L # k|ljwf ljsl;t 5g\ eg] sljtfsf d'Qms, km'6s/ sljtf, v08sfJo, dxfsfJo h:tf k|ljwfxč 5g\ . Psf^a\sL / k"Off{^a\sL gf6ssf k|ljwf x'g\ eg] lgaGwleq cfTdk/s, ;+:d/OffTds , ofqfk/s -lgofqf_, hLjgLk/s -z^a\s/ nfld5fg]sf] laDa k|ltlaDa_ cflb wf/xč ljsl;t ePsf 5g\ . oL wf/xčnfO{ k|ljwf eGg'eGbf k|sf/ eGg' pko'Qm xf]nf . k|ljwfsf s'/f ubf{ cfVofgdf ;"qsyf h:tf n]vgsf] k|of]u yflnPsf] 5 . o:t} sljtfdf t cem w]/) k|of]uxč k|rngdf 5g\ . 8f= o1]Zj/ lg/f]nfn] ...'g]kfnL sljtfsf n3'td pkljwf' ljifos uf]i7Lkqdf xfn;Dd sljtf ljwfsf #^ pkljwf k|of]udf /x]sf] s'/f pNn]v u/]sf 5g\ . pgsf cg';f/ sljtf ljwdf xfn;Dd d'Qms, xfOs', l;hf], t^a\sf, ;]Go', ;]bf]sfs, ?jfo, Pnfs, ;fOgf], sf]lknf, afl56f, ;';]nL, pbs, vf]l/of, lqmd's, em/, 5]:sf, tKsgf, lk/fld8, /Daf;, 6'qmf, 5f]s, s'6kB, ;fo/L, bf]xf, ;f]/7f, rf}kfO, cfNxf, k'/aL, s];|f, lvr8L, o'Uds, cfuf], zLt, ltkfnL, k~rf^a\u h:tf pkljwf 5g\ . n]vs lg/f]nfn] logLxčnfO{ pkljwf eg] klq oL sljtf ljwfsf n]vgdf /x]sf k|of]u x'g\ . o:t} ;dfnf]rgfsf] wf/nfO{ klS8P/ xfn lg;dfnf]rgf eGg] k|of]u klq yflnPsf] 5 . oL k|of]uxčdWo] sltko k|of]udf t k':ts g] klq n]lv;lsPsf] 5 . t/ Pp6f c^a\u|]hL pvfg 5 – Ps b'O{ j6f uf]FynL cfpFb]df u|Lid Ct' cfpGg . eg]sf] dtna oL k|of]uxč k|ljwfsf :jčkdf bl/gsf nflu To;df cem Jofkstf cfpG h?/L 5 .

Inlvt ;flxTosf /x]sf pkljwfnfO{ csf]{ zAbdf k|ljwf klq elgG5 . ljwf ;dfj]zL zAb xf] eg] k|ljwf ;df]ji6 zAb xf] . ;flxTodf k|ljwfxč ;doqmddf ljsl;t eO/xG5g\ . ;flxTosf ljwfsf k|ljwfxč slxNo} klq ?9 x'Fb}gg\ / x'g' klq x'Fb}g . ?9tf t ljsf;sf] jfws xf] . k|ljwfTds ljsf; hlt w]/) x'G5 Tolt g] ljwfsf] JofKttf a9\5 . ox]Fg]/ Pp6f s'/f s] a'em\g'k5{ eg] ;flxTosf ljwfxčsf] k|of]udf aGb]h x'g'x'Fb}g . lsgeg]

;flxTosf k|of]uxč ha kl/kSj aG5g\ ta ltgn] k|ljwfsf :jčk u|x0f u5{g\ . ha ljwfsf k|ljwfxč a9\5g\ To;n] ljwfnfO{ ;d'Ggltsf] dfu{lt/ n}hfG5 . g]kfnL ;flxTodf d"n ljwdf k|of]uxč k|z:t ePsf 5g\ .

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t/ tL dWo] Jofkstf kfPsf s]xL k|of]uxčn] dfq k|ljwf aGg] ;f}efUo k|fKt u/]sf] 5 . k|ljwf eg]sf d"n 3/af6 5'6\6fleGgf ePsf bfh'efO h:tf x'g\ hf] kfl/jfl/s čkdf Ps} xFufleqsf eP klg k/lge{/tfsf] dfu{ 5f8]/ cf^gf] cl:tTj lgdf{Of ul/;s]sf x'G5g\ . ha;Dd ljwfsf k|of]uxčsf] s'/f 5 tL k|ljwfsf čkdf ljsl;t geP;Dd d"n ljwfs} ;]stfkdf /xG5g\ .

;flxTosf ljleGg ljwfdWo] cfVofg ljwfsf] Pp6f dxČEjk"Of{ k|ljwfsf čkdf ljsl;t 5 – n3'syf . of] n3'td cfVofg xf] . of] lxF8\g] km/s lns 5 . o;sf] cfČg} lsl;dsf] n]vgz}nL ljsl;t 5 . of] pkGof;h:tf] klg xf]Og / syfh:tf] klg xf]Og . sljtfsf ljwf / pkljwfxčeGbf n3'syf leGg 5g\ . lgaGw, ;+d/Of, hLjgL cflbsf z}nL;Fu n3'syfsf] k|j[IQ km/s 5 . 5f]6f] / I56f]df cufl8 a9\g' n3'syfsf] k|j[IQwld{tf xf] . of] Ps p2]Zos]Gb|L ljwf xf] . o;}n] xFufla+uf;lxtsf] ;+/rgfnfO{ o;n] af]Sb}g . o;df syfj:t', kfq, kl/j]z cflbsf] pkof]u ubf{ Psn nlfnfO{ Wofgdf /fvL ul/G5 . o;f] x'g'nfO{ n3'syfsf] Psf]Gd'v k|j[IQ eGg ;lsG5 . oxL k|j[IQn] ubf{ n3'syfsf/nfO{ axlsg] jf JofVof ug]{ k'm;{b x'Fb}g . oxL sf/Of n3'syfn] /}lvs 9fFrnfO{ a9L dgk/fPsf] x'G5 .

n3'syf cfVofgsf c? k|ljwfxč pkGof; / syf h:tf] nfd] Oltxf; ePsf] k|ljwf xf]Og t/ o;f] eGb}df of] k|of]udf dfq ;Lldt /x]sf] klg 5}g . n]vg, k|sfzg, k|;f/Of, k7g, ljZn]if0f cflbdf o;sf] bfo/f cfzfnfUbf] lsl;daf6 km}ln/x]sf] 5 . of] pkGof; / syfsf] bfFhf]df cfpg g;s] klg k|ljwfsf čkdf eg] ljsl;t eO;s]sf] 5 .

cWoog ljlw / k|lqmof

o; cfn]vdf xfnsf] bzsd] ljsf;sf] pSnfOdf /x]sf] n3'syfnfO{ cfVofg clg cfVofg]t/ ljwf k|ljwf;Fu t'ngf u/L Itgsf aLrdf /x]sf] ;DaGw c;DaGwnfO{ s]nfpFb} lgisif{ ;d]t lgsflnPsf] 5 . of] k':tsfno ljlwdf /x]/ ul/Psf] u'OffTds cg';Gwfg sfo{ xf] . n3'syf / cGo ljwfk|ljwfsf lar s'g};Fu lgs6td / s'g};Fu b"/td ;DaGw /xg;Sg] s'/fnfO{ o;df ljZn]if0fsf ;fy lgrf]8 lbOPsf] 5 . ox]F pkof]u ul/Psf] ljlw j0f{gfTds / ljZn]if0ffTds ljlw g} xf] . ox]F cfjZos kb{f t'ngfTdstfnfO{ klg ckgfOPsf] 5 . lâtLos ;|f]tsf ;fdu|LxčnfO{ o; cWoogdf pkof]u ul/Psf] 5 . g]kfnL ;flxTodf n3'syfsf] :yfg lgwf{/Of ug'{ o;sf] d'Vo p2]Zo xf] . cGo ljwfk|ljwf / n3'syf a'em\g rfxg]xčsf nflu of] n]v pkof]uL x'g]5 .

cfVofgsf tLg k|ljwf M pkGof;; syf / n3'syf

cfVofg ljwfsf tLg k|ljwf ljsl;t ePsf 5g\ . oL tLg k|ljwfdWo] pkGof; a[xb\, syf n3' / n3'syf n3'td cfsf/sf 5g\ .

pkGof; M cfVofgsf] a[xb\ čk

pkGof; cfVofgsf] a[xb\ čk xf] . o;sf] P]ltxf]stfsf] kfgf kN6fpFb} hfg] xf] eg] s/Lj t]O; ;o jif{ cufl8;Dd k'luG5 . pkGof; zAbsf] klxnf] k|of]u ug]{ cfrfo{ e/td'lg x'g\ . pgn] cfČgf] gf6\ozf:qdf o;sf] pNn]v u/]sf 5g\ . zflAbs k|of]u t efdx, b08L, wg~ho, ljZjgfy]n] klg u/]sf] e]l6G5 . o; k|ljwfd]f ;+s]t ;flxTon] lbPsf] eg]sf] zAb k|of]u / k"jf{efif dfq xf] . pkGof;sf] jf:tljs gflna]nLsf

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nflu eg] klZrddf g} k'Ug'k5{ . klZrddf To;df klG c^u|]hL ;flxTon] xfd|f]df pkGof; elgg] zAbnfO{ kof{os} :jckdf gf]a]n eg]sf] 5 . gf]a]n zAb Nofl6gsf] gf]a;\ / gf]an;\ x'Fb] ljsl;t O6flnogsf] gf]a]n zAbs} ckfGt/ xf] elgG5 . O6flnog n]vs lucf]jfgL af]sfl;ofaf/f lnlt 8]sfd]/fF s[ltnfO{ gf]a]n elgPsf]n] klZrddf pkGof; gfd lbP/} cfPsf] klxnf] s[lit g} o;}nfO{ dflgPsf] 5 . O{ZjLsf] !#\$* b]lv !#%* ;Ddsf syfxck 8]sfd]/fFdf ;d]l6Psf]n] klZrddf o;sf] P]ltxfl;stf OZjLsf] rf}wf}F ztfAbLlt/sf] b]vfk5{ .

syfgs, rl/q, syf]ksyg, z}nL, efff, jftfj/Of, p2]Zo h:tf lgdf{Of pks/Ofxckaf6 ;lhPsf] pkGof; syfs} hudf plePsf] x'G5 . cfVofgsf] n3' ck syf / n3'td ck n3'syf;Fu o;sf] ;xf]b/ gftf 5 . z}nLut ckdf x]bf{ o;df uB z}nLsf] k|of]u ul/Psf] x'G5 . hLjgsf] ;du| cknfO{ o;df ;d]l6Psf] x'G5 clg w|/} kfqxck k|of]u ul/G5g\ . n]vgdf ljZn]if0ffTdstf / ljj/0ffTdstfsf] pkof]u x'G5 . pkGof;n] hLjg / ;dfh n]V5 t/ x'jx' xf]Og . sfNklgstfsf] w/ftndf pleP/ of] aU5 . pkGof;n] n]vgdf s:tf] af6f] ckgfpF5 eGg] ;DaGwdf ljj]rs s[i0frGb| l;Fx k|wfg o:tf] ts{ /fV5g\ -

æpkGof;n] cfGtl/s / afXo k|j]lQxcksf] lrqOf u|/ hLjgnfO{ gfK5 / To;sf] d"no vf]H5 . ;dfhnfO{ 7DofpF5 / df]8\g] k|oTg u5{, ultnfO{ ;dfpF5 / lbzf lbG ;^s]t u5{ . o;/L k|]/Off lbO/xG5 . s]jn oyftYotf pb\3f6g x]g, dg'io ;dfhsf] cWoog o;df ceLlk;t x'G5 . lsgeg] lj1fg tyf bz{g k|ltkflbt ;To g} ;Dk"Of{ xf]Og . j]1flgs tYoeGbf k/sf] ;TonfO{ pkGof;n] l6K5 / Tot} k|]/t u5{ .Æ

-k|wfg, @)%@, k[= @_ pkGof;nfO{ cfVofgsf] a[xb\ ck elgP klG cfs[ltsf lx;fn] of] klG n3', a[xb\ / a[xQd x'g;S5 . ;?eQm lnlt r'nL, s]zj/fh lkF8fnL lnlt afFRg] Pp6f lhGbuL clg nLnaxfb'/ lf]qL lnlt a;ofFnfO{ n3' pkGof;sf] >]0fLdf /fVg ;lsG5 eg] kb\dfjtL l;Fx lnlt ;dfgfGt/ cfsfz, bf}ntliqmd lai6 lnlt rkfOPsf cg'xf/, w|'jrGb| uf}td lnlt clnlvtnfO{ a[xb\ / dbgdlof bLlft lnlt dfwjL, bf}ntlaqmd lji6 lnlt Hof]lt Hof]lt dxhHof]ltnfO{ a[xQd leq /fVg ;lsG5 . o;sf] n]vgdf s'g} cfsf/ut ;Ldf 5}g .

syf M cfVofgsf] n3' ck k|To]s ljwf tyf k|ljwfsf] cf/lDes p7fgsf] s'/f ubf{ k''j{df j]b / klZrddf k|frLg u|Ls;Dd k'u]/ y/s df]/G5 . syfsf] h/f vf]Hbf klG ToxLF g} k'Ug'sf] ljsNk 5}g . t/ cfhsf syfsf cfsf/k|sf/ clg ljifo / z}nLnfO{ x]/]/ o;sf] k|frLgtf s]nfpG;Dej 5}g . k''j{df j]b / klZrddf k|frLg u|Lsdf k'Ubf cfhsf syfsf k''j{efif eg] k|fKt ug{ ;lsG5 . j]bxckdf ;a}eGbf k|frLg elgPsf] CUj]bdf syf ;^s]t dfq kfOP klG j|fXdOf u|Gyxckdf

eg] t'ngfTds ckdf syfsf] cfefif cln a9L ;3g aGb} uPsf] ;^s]t b]lvPsf] 5 . o;f] egf}F - j]bdf eGbf j|fXdOf u|Gyxckdf, j|fXdOf u|Gyxckdf eGbf pklgifb\ckdf / pklgifb\ckdf eGbf nf]lss ;+:s[tsf s[ltxckdf syftOej qmdzM k|uf9 aGb} uPsf] 5 . k''j{df k|frLg syfsf] k/Dk/f ;^s]tsf ckdf g} ;xL k|i6 5 t/ klZrddf cfGg} k|i6 syf hu e]l6Gg . klZrdsf] syf hu eg]sf] ld>]nL, lxGb', lxa|" / c/a]nL k|frLg lv;:f g} xf] .

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log} k"j{sf hudf 6}s]/ klZrdn] syfsf] ejo dxn lgdf{Of u/]sf x'g\ . of] s'/fdf xfd|f] dfq lhls/ xf]Og o;df klZrdsf] klg k"Of{ l:jsf/f]lQm 5 . k"j{df syfsf] sf];] 9'a\uf aGg] >]o nf]lss ;flxTosf klxnf cflbslj elgg] jfNdLlss[t /fdfo0fn] k|fKt u/]sf] 5 eg] klZrddf k|frLg lu|;]nL ;flxTosf/ xf]d/s[t Olno8 / cf]l8l;n] k|fKt u/]sf] 5 . oBlk k"j{ / klZrddf sf];]9'a\ufsf] sfd ug]{ oL s[ltxç eg] ljwfut çkdf sljtf / k|ljwfut çkdf dxfsf]Jo x'g\ . Itgdf syfTdstfsf] d'xf/ /fd|f];Fu emlNsPsf] 5 t/ olt eGbfeGb} klg cfhsf syfsf] d'xf/ lxhf]sf tL d'xf/df eg] vf]Hg' dgfl;a x'Fb}g . sf/Of lxhf]b]lv aUb} cfPsf tL syf gbLxçdf cfh lgs} 7'nf kl/jt{gxç cfO;s]sf 5g\ .

syf cfVofgsf] n3' cyf{t\ demf}nf] çk xf] . dflysf k|;a\unfO{ l;/fgL xfn]/ x]bf{ klg of] lgs} a'9f]k'/fgf] / l5IKkPsf] k|ljwf xf] eGg] klg k'li6 x'G5 . tœjut çkdf x]bf{ pkGof;;Fu syfsf] gftf k|dfOfLs/Of ug{ ;lhnf] 5 . t/ pks/Ofut k|of]unfO{ x]g]{ xf] eg] pkGof;df eGbfeGbf syfdf k|of]usf] cNktf k|i6 5 . syfnfO{ n3'çksf] cfVofg elgP klg o;sf] cfsf/k|sf/ tLg :çkdf 5g\ --!_ clt nfdf syf -@_ nfdf syf / -#_ 5f]6f syf . g]kfnLdf clt nfdf syf n]Vg] rng vf; } 5}g, nfdf / 5f]6f syf eg] e]l6G5g\ . oxf 5f]6f syf eGg'sf] dtmj n3'syf eGg' eg] xf]Og . n3'syfsf 9'a\uf / 9fFr 5f]6f syfeGbfeGbf lgtfGt km/s 5g\ .

n3'syf M cfVofgsf] n3'td çk n3'td ljz]iftf /x]sf] n3'syf cfVofgsf] t];|f] k|e]b xf] . o;nfO{ cfVofgsf] sfG5f] k|ljwf eGg ;lsG5 . cfVofgsf pkGof; / syfem}F o;sf] klg nx/f] tflgFb} hfFbf k"j{ / klZrdsf cflbsfnf cfVofgfTds /rgf;Dd k'U5 . k"j{ / klZrdsf n3'sfo lnP/ cfPsf syf+zxçdf o;sf] 3'd}{nf] 5lj b]Vg ;lsG5 . k"j{df j]b, j|fxDof u|Gy, pklgfb\ tyf k'/f0fxçdf n3'syfsf ememNsf] lb] syf+zxç oy]i6 e]l6G5g\ . klZrddf ld>]nL, lxGb', lxa|" / c/a]nL k|frLg lv;:fxçn] n3'syfsf] clncln lgof;|f] d]6\5 . klZrdn] n3'syfdf ljleGg k|of]u u/]sf] 5 t/ xfd|fdf eg] Tolt w]/) k|of]u e]l6Gg . klZrddf n3'syfsf] kof{o]frL gfd lgs} 5g\ . tL dWo] s]xL x'g\ – Short Short Story -n3'syf_, Very Very Short Story -cToNk syf_, Little Short Story -;fg' syf_, Mini Story -5l/tf] syf_, Flash Story -bLlKt syf_, Micro Story -ldxLF syf_, Hint Story -;a\s]t syf_,

Postcard fiction -8fskq] syf_, Nano fiction -gfg' syf_, Drabble -8«ofan syf_, Twitter fiction -l6\j6/ syf_, Sudden Story -;8g syf_ cflb . oL gfdxç ;dfnf]rs df]xg/fh zdf{n] cf^gf] ;dfnf]rgfTds s[lit ;dfnf]rgfsf] gofF sf]Ofsf] n3'syfsf] lrgf/L / g]kfnL n3'syf eGg] PsfOdf pNn]v u/]sf 5g\ . klZrdn] n3'syf eg]/ u/]sf oL k|of]uxçdf gfddf dfq leGgtf geP/ ;+/rgf / k|:t'ltxçdf klg clncln leGgtf 5 . g]kfnLsf n3'syfdf #)) zAbsf] cf;kf;df /x]/ n]lv]g] z}nL a9L k|rlnt 5 . s]xLn] cfhsn ;"qsyf eg]/ klg o;sf] k[ys\ k|of]u yfn]sf 5g\ . ;dfnf]rs df]xg/fh zdf{n] n3'syfsf n]vsxç Ps} k|of]udf dfq gu'h'IN6P/ ljljw k|of]utkm{ nfUg'kg]{ s'/fsf] ;a\s]t ub} eg]sf 5g\ –

æ;dsfnLg g]kfnL ;flxTodf ca k|rlnt 9/f{df xr'jf lsl;dn] s'g} Pp6f zAb;a\Vof -h:t} %)) ;Dd jf #)) ;Dd_ tf]sL To;adf]lhd n3'syf n]Vb}df k'Ub}g ca Pp6f dfq xf]Og, ljljw zAb;a\Vof tf]sL of]hgfa4 çkdf ;fy{s Pjd\ k|efjsf/L n3'syf n]Vg' cfjZos

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5 . s'g} zAb;ª\Vof tf]sL To; ;Ldfleq /x]/ Tolt;Ddsf] jf To;eGbf sd zAbsf] n3'syf /rgfsf] ;fy} lglZrt ;ª\Vof tf]sL To;eGbf k6Ss} 36a9 gu/L Tolt zAbd} syf n]Vg' klg h?/L eO;s]sf] 5 . ===== cr]n ;a} n3'syfxç bLlKt syf jf lemNsf] syfsf çkdf /lrg] x'Fbf lgwf{l/t zAb;ª\Vof hlt eP klg /rgf lah'nLem}F rDs}/ cy{bLlKt k|bfg ug}{ vfnsf] x'g'k5{ .Æ -zdf{, @}&*, k[= #@&_ n3'syfsf] cfÇg} :jçk / ;+/rgf 5 . o;sf] :jçk / ;+/rgf cGo ljwf k|ljwf;Fu ldNof] ldNof] h:tf] eP klg km/s 5 . o;df syfgssf cflb, dWo / cGTosf] >[ª\vnf /xG5 . o:tf] >[ª\vnf pkGof; / syfdf klg x'G5 . cfsf/df 7'nf] x'g] x'Fbf pkGof;df of] >[ª\vnfn] ljsl;t x'g] ;do k|z:t kfpF5 . pkGof;df cflb / cGTo efunfO{ Ps Ps j6f kl/R5]bdf / dWo efunfO{ ljleGg kl/R5]bxçdf km}nfpG ldN5 . syf eg] demf]nf] k|ljwf ePsf] To;df oL cª\uxç pkGof;df hlt km}ng kfpGgg\ . cem n3'syfdf t o;sf] km}nfj6nfO{ lgs} ;fF3'¥ofpg' kg}{ x'G5 . lsgls n3'syfsf] d"n ;"q g} ...'5f]6f] n]v, l56f] n]v / k|efjsf/L n]v' xf] . n3'syfdf Hofb} n3'td ;+/rgfdf cflb, dWo / cGTosf] >[ª\vnf lvKg' kg}{ ePsf] o;sf] n]vg r'gf}tLk"Of{ klg 5 .

n3'syfsf] cflb efu cf/De xf] . cf/De eg]sf] ljifosf] p7fg . o;} efudf ;d:of /f]lkG5, ;d:of cª\s'/Of x'G5 / åGåjLh pTkfbg x'G5 . o;sf cf/lDes jfSoxç cf]lhnf x'g' cfjZos 5 lsgls of] kf7ssf] Wofg lvRg] cª\u xf] . dfgssf] ;'?jft oxL ljGb'af6 x'g] ePsf] klg n3'syfsf/n] z]nLut kl/kSjtf oxLFaf6 yfNg'k5{ . oxfF JofVof rflxGg / ljZn]ifOf /flvGg . ;"qfTds k|ljw pkof]u ul/G5 .

cflb efudf /f]lkPsf] / pld|Psf] ;d:ofn] pTisf{tf k|fkt ug}{ 7fpF dWo efu g} xf] . åGåsf] p7fg / ljsf; clg sf}t'xnsf] pb\ej / pTisf{ klg oxL+ x'G5 . åGånfO{ ;3g agfpg] 7fpF klg oxLF g} xf] . åGå hlt ;3g eof] Tolt g} dfqfdf kf7sleq x'F8nf] dlRrG5 . kf7sleq hlt x'F8nf] / tgj a9\of] Tolt g} w]/} n3'syf ;kmn aG5 .

cGTo efu eg]sf] n3'syfsf] aL6 xf] . of] alnof] u/L a'lgg' k5{ . cflb / dWo efusf] ;kmntfn] dfq n3'syfsf] dfgs lgwf{/Of x'Fb}g . o;}n of] efudf rf]l6nf jfSoxçsf] pkof]u x'g'k5{ . cGTo Joj:yfkg ;a} ljwf k|ljwdfd rflxG5 t/ n3'syfsf] cGTo efu c? ljwfsf] h:tf] x'Fb}g . n3'syfn] cGTo Joj:yfkgdf ljnDa xf]Og cfsl:dstf vf]H5 . cfsl:dstfn] kf7snfO{ vNaNofpF5 . oxfF kf7s hlt a9L vNalnof] Tolt g} n3'syf ;kmn aG5 . oxfF n3'syfsf/n] pkb]z xf]Og ljrj/nfO{ :yflkt ug{' k5{ . o;n] lj:tf/sf] ky ;dft]sf] x'Fb}g . of] 5f]6f] af6af6 l56f] uGtJodf k'U5 . n3'syfdf r'6\lsnf aGg] hf]lvd /xG5 . n]vs o;k|lt rgfvf] gx'Fbf n3'syfn] lflt a]xf]g' k5{ . o; ;DaGwdf ;dLlfs k|f=8f= bof/fd >]i7sf] wf/Off o:tf] 5 –

ælj:tf/df qmd};Fu hfg' o;sf] :jefj lsdyf{ xf]Og tfklg cfÇgf] /}lvs ultnfO{ eg] o;n] zL3|fltZL3| kf/ u/L cGTodf kf7sdf ulx/f] k|ltWjlg -Eco Sound_ sf] cfefif u/fp/ 5f8\5 . k|ltWjlg g;'lgP Tof] n3'/rgf n3'syf geP/ s'g} 76\of]nL -Jokes_ dfq aG5 .Æ ->]i7, @)&*, k[= !#_

n3'syfnfO{ cGTo ug]{ @ z]nL 5g\ – vf]Ng] z]nL / 5f]Kg] z]nL . oxfF vf]Ng] / 5f]Kg]sf] dtnj cy{ vf]Ng] / cy{ gv]Ng] elgPsf] xf] . vf]Ng] z]nLdf n]vsn] lgOf{o lbG5 eg] 5f]Kg] z]nLdf

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n]vsn] lgOf{o lbFb}g . vf]Ng] z}nLdf cfzo vf]Hg kf7s 3f]ITng kb}{g eg] 5f]Kg] z}nLdf cy{sf nflu kf7s 3f]ITng' k5{ . vf]Ng] z}nL cy{sf} kmf]s; n3'syfsf/ :jo+n] lgwf{/Of ug}{ z}nL xf] eg] 5f]Kg] z}nL n]vsn] kf7snfO{ lbPsf] u[xsfo{ xf] . elgG5

– kf7ssf] dgdflkms wf/Off agfpg] / ;f]rdUg x'g] clwsf/nfO{ vf]Ng] z}nLn] s'lO7t agfpg] x'Fbf /fd|f] xf]Og . o;}n] n3'syf n]vsẋnfO{ ;'emfj lbFbf 5f]Kg] z}nL g] pkof]u ug{ elgG5 . t/ sltko n]vsẋn] cfÇgf] p2]Zo Psflt/ / kf7ssf] a'emfO csf]{lt/ x'g] cj:yf /f]Sg hfgfhfg vf]Ng] z}nL /f]H5g\ . of] vf]Ng] z}nL eg]sf] klg ;'rLsf/sf] ;Lk h:t} xf] . sk8ssf] l8hfOg ubf{ slt vf]Nbf /fd|f] / slt vf]Nbf e2f x'G5 eGg] s'/f s'zn ;'rLsf/sf] ;Lk / cg'ejn] to u/] h:t} Pp6f s'zn n3'syfsf/n] klg ;dfkgdf slt vf]Ng] / slt 5f]Kg] eGg] s'zntf b]vfpdf n3'syfsf] :t/Lotf 36\b}g a9\5 . t/ of] vf]Ng] z}nLsf] pkof]u ubf{ n]vsn] cToGt s'zntf eg] k|bz{g ug{'k5{ . o;}n] oxF s] eGg ;lsG5 eg] vf]Ng] z}nLsf] pkof]u ug]{ xf] eg] n]vsn] cf^gf] p2]Zosf] ;^s]t dfq u/f];\, kf7sLo lh1f;fsf] ;Dk"Of{ cfofdẋ aGb ug]{ u/L o;sf] k|of]u gu/f];\ .

t'ngfTds lgisif{

cfVofgsf tLg k|ljwf 5g\ — pkGof;, syf / n3'syf . oL # j6} k|ljwfẋ :jtGq klg 5g\ . x'gt Ps] ljwfsf k|ljwf ePsf]n] logdf sltko b[li6n] ;fDotf b]lvG' cgf}7f] xf]Og . lgdf{Of pks/Ofẋ ldNbfh'Nbf 5g\ t/ pkof]usf] t/Lsf / dfqdf km/s 5 . oL tLg k|ljwfẋ 36gf, kfq / kl/]zsf b[li6n] km/s 5g\ . pkGof;df w]/} 36gfẋ x'G5g\ — Ps d'Vo df]6f] 36gf / ToxL d'Vo df]6f] 36gfnfO{ 3]g{ cfpg] cGo ;xfos 36gfẋ . b'?:t Pp6f dflg;sf] ;du| hLjgh:tf] hxfF cgluGtL kfqẋ 7f]ISsg cfOk'U5g\, rl/qsf] j]xb\ ljsf; x'G5, JofVofTds k|j]lQ b]vfk5{ / km}lnPsf] v'nf kl/]z ;fllfTsf/ x'G5 . bf];|f] k|ljwf syf hxfF d'Vo 36gf / cfjZostfcg';f/ Psb'O{ j6f ;xfos 36gfẋ klg /xG5g\ t/ o;df ;xfos 36gfẋsf] hfnf] eg] /xGg . kfq x'G5g\ t/ ;Lldt . kl/]zdf /xG5 — t'ngfTds ċkdf JofVofTds / lj:tf/fTds :yltsf] ;^s'rg . Jo^Uor]t lzlyn x'G5 . hLjgsf] Ps v08] k|:t'lt egf]+ syfnfO{ . cyf{t\ of] -syf_ hLjg xf]Og, hLjgdf dxĈej /fVg] Ps 36gf . t];|f] k|ljwf n3'syf xf], h;df Pp6f cToGt ;fgf] / dl;gf] 36gf /xG5 . sDtLdf @ 36gf x'g'k5{ . Ps dfq 36gf hLjGt n3'syfsf nflu /fd|f] xf]Og . w]/} 36gfẋsf] hfnf] klg n3'syfn] y]Ug ;Sb}g . kfqẋ klg x'G5g\ o;df t/ rl/q lraqOf x'Gg . kl/]z ;^s]tTds, cJofVofTds / clj:tf/fTds x'G5 . wfl/nf] Jo^Uor]tgf, ;3g k|tLsfTdstf n3'syfsf bl/nf j]lzi6\o x'g\ . ljâfg\ ẋn] syfnfO{ k|lqmofaf6 vf]lhg] nlf / n3'syfnfO{ nife]bgsf] ;fwgf eg]sf 5g\ . k|Vof cfVofg n]vs k|]drGbn] syf / pkGof;sf] k[ys\tf s]nfpFb} æsyfdf rl/qsf] emns x'G5 eg] pkGof;df emfFsLÆ eg]sf 5g\ .

syf / n3'syf ;x;DaGwL ljwf /x]sf] s'/f k|i6 kfb}{ l;4fGtsf/ nldOfk|;fb uf}td eG5g\ –

n3'syf klg syf g] ePsf]n] syfsf h]h:tf 36s, n3';+rs tĈej jf pks/Of x'G5g\ syfdf klg ltg} pks/Ofẋsf] ljGof; x'G5 / syf n3'syf b'a} cfVofgsf k|e]b ePsf]n] klg oL b'O{sf aLr ;x;DaGw b]lvG5 . -uf}td, @)&@, k[= *#_

syf / n3'syfsf] cGt/nfO{ k|i6 kfb}{ lxGbL ;dLlfs >L ;tLz/fh k'is/Offn] eg]sf 5g\ –

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æn3'syf dfq syfgssf] :t/af6 g} syfeGbf leGg x'G5 . n3'syfdf d"ntM Ps dfq lfl0fs

36gf x'G5, h;df ;do cGt/fnsf] s'g} u'GhfO; x'Fb}g .Æ Æ -k'is/Off, @)!,(k[= @!%_ lxGbL ;flxTosf ;dLlfs lgzfGt/ syfsf] lrgf/Ldf n]V5g\ — æsyfdf PseGbf a9L cnu cnu sfnv08sf], Pscsf{;Fu ;Da4 cnu cnu 36gfox'G5, Ps syfTdstfsf] ;"qdf hf]8]/ hLjgsf] s'g} Ps cª\ u jf s'g} Ps dgf]efjnfO{ k|blz{t ul/Psf] x'G5 .Æ -lgzfGt/, @)!,(k[= #*_ ljj]rs kmf]sg/n] syf / pkGof; n]vgsf ;DaGwdf t'ngf ub}{ eg]sf 5g\ –

æpkGof; n]Vbf lgs} lgl:kmqmL x'g ;lsG5 . o;df w]/} lg/y{s sl;ª\ u/ klg ld;fpg ;lsG5 / h] u/] klg To;df 5'6 x'G5 t/ syf eg]sf] sljtf kl5sf] ljwf ePsf] syfsf] k|To]s zAb ;6Ls / pko'Qm 7fpFdf /;fOPsf] x'g'k5{ . pkGof;df tkfO{+ nfk/jafxL ug{ ;Sg'x'G5 t/ syfdf To;f] ug{ ;Sg'x'Gg . r]v]n] n]v]h:tf pTs[i6 syfnfO{ x[bodf /fv]/ d]n] To;f] eg]sf] x'F . To;]n] d]n] syfnfO{ bf];|f] :yfgdf /fv]sf] x'F . syfsf]/tfd] clwstd lgvf/ jf kl/isf/sf] cfjZostf kb{5 . nfk/jfxL ug{ jf glrNofOsg 5f8\g] cj;/ Toxf sDtL k|fKt x'G5 . Toxf sl;ª\ u/sf] lglDt sDtL cj;/ k|fKt x'G5 . oBlk sljtfdf eg] sl;ª\ /sf lglDt clnslt klg cj;/ k|fKt x'Gg . of] l]z'4, lGzrn / cToGt} k"Of{ x'g'kb{5 .Æ -;dsfnLg ;flxTo k"Of{ª\ s !, @)%), k[= (@_ ljleGg ljwf;Fu n3'syfsf] ;DaGw c;DaGw n3'syf / d'Qms aLr k|j][lQhGo lgs6tf kfOG5 . oL b'a]n] cg'e"ltsf] lemNsf]nfO{ cleJoQm u5{g\ . n3'td /rgf x'g' b'a]sf] kl/ro xf] . hLjghut\sf] lraqOf, k|of]hg / k|efjsf]/tfsf b[li6n] oL ;dfg 5g\ . oL b'a]df sYok'li6sf nflu qmdzM kl5Nnf jfSo jf kª\ltxç ;3g aGb} hfG5g\ . oL b'a]n] kf7sLo dl:tisdf zAbu'~hgsf] t/ª\ u k|jflxt u5{g\ . zAbu'~hgsf] t/ª\ u hlt nfd] ;do;Dd /xG5 Tolt g} oL b'a} k|efjsf/L /rgf aG5g\ . o:tf k|j][lQut ;fdLKotf x'Fbf'Fb} klg oL b'O{ Pp6} ljwfsf k|ljwf eg] xf]Ogg\ . n3'syf cfVofg ljwfsf] k|ljwf xf] eg] d'Qms sljtf ljwfsf] k|ljwf xf] . n3'syf uBfTds /rgf xf] eg] d'Qms kBfTds /rgf xf] . uBz]nL k|wfg x'g} ePsf] n3'syfdf u]ofTds k|j][lQ kfOGg eg] kBz]nL k|wfg x'gfn] d'Qmsdf u]ofTds u'Of e]l6G5 . ;+/rgfTds b[li6n] b'a} ljGb' x'g\ l;Gw' xf]Ogg\ t/ a]hf]8 cy{k|jfxsf b[li6n] b'a} ljGb'leqsf l;Gw' x'g\ . n3'syf / d'Qms aLr /x]sf] ;DaGw k|i6 kfb}{ ;dLlfs nld0fk|;fb uf}tdn] cfÇgf] k':tsdf eg]sf 5g\ – n3'syf / d'Qms k"Of{tof leGg leGg k|ljwf x'g\ t/ sYo, efj, cg'e"lt cflbsf] pQ/f]Q/ tLa|tf / /x:osf] k6fif]k h:tf s]xL /rgfljwfg / qmdzM cfVofg / sljtsf n3'td çksf sf/Of eg] n3'syf / d'Qmssf aLr ;x;DaGw b]lvG5 . -uf}td, @)&@, k[= *\$ _

syf / d'Qmsb]lv jfx]s cGo ljwfk|ljwf;Fu n3'syfsf] ;fdLKotf eGbf b"/tf a9L b]lvG5 . sljtf ljwf cGtu{t kg}{ dxsfJo, v08sfJo, nfd] sljtf, km'6s/ sljtsf ;fy} lgaGw, k|aGw, hLjgL, cfTdj][QfGt, gf6s cflb ljwfk|ljwf;Fu ;flxITos cleJolQm x'g' jfx]s n3'syfsf] ;DaGw b]lvGg . rf]l6nf] cleJolQm ePsf cfwf/df n3'syf;Fu r'6\lsnfsf] lgs6tf 5 t eGg ;lsPnf t/ cy{ufDeLo{tfsf lx;fjn] oL b'O{ lgs} 6f9f 5g\ . n3'syf uDeL/ /rgf xf] eg] r'6\lsnf nf]s 76\of]nL xf] . r'6\lsnf lfl0fs dgf]/~hg xf] eg] n3'syf hLjGt ;flxITos /rgf xf] . cfhsf sltko n]vxsçn] r'6\lsnf / n3'syf aLrsf] e]b 5'6\ofpg g;Sbf

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n3'syfsf gfddf r'6\lsnf n]lv/x]sf 5g\ . r'6\lsnfafhLaf6 n3'syfnfO{ arfpg' n3'syfsf] r'gf}tL xf] . o:t} cfofdsf b[li6n] n3'syf;Fu ;"lQmkB, 5f]6f gLltsyf / nf]ssyfsf] ;DaGw b]lvP klG cGo b[li6n] oL km/s x'g\ .

n3'syfdf sljtf gf6s / lgaGwsf] cGt3'{ng eg} ePsf] kFOG5 . Ps ljwfleq csf]{ ljwfsf] k|lji6nfO{ ljwfxçsf] cGt3'{ng elG5 . of] ljwfld>0fsf] cj:yf xf] . of] ljlgdf{0fsf] Pp6f k|lqmof xf] . sljtf, gf6s / lgaGwafx]s cGo ljwfsf] n3'syfdf cGt3'{ng x'Fb}g . sljtf ljwf cGt3'{Int n3'syfxç sfJofTds n3'syf x'g\ . d'Qm nofTdstf o;sf] k|j[lQ xf] . gf6s ljwf cGt3'{ng ePsf n3'syfxç gf6\ofTds n3'syf x'g\ .

o:tf n3'syfxçdf ;+jfbfTds k|j[lQ e]l6G5 . lgaGw ljwf ldl>t n3'syf lgaGwfTds z}nLsf n3'syf x'g\ . o:tf n3'syfdf cfTdk/s z}nL / k|ydk'?if k|ydk'?if b[li6ljGb'sf] k|of]u x'G5 . lgaGw ldl>t n3'syfdf cfVofgtÇEjsf] eg] Go"gtf /xG5 . o:tf ljwf cGt3'{Int k|j[lQn] n3'syfnfO{ k|of]uzLn agfO{ ljsl;t t'Nofpg ;xof]u k'¥ofPsf] x'G5 .

ljleGg ljwf k|ljwf;Fu n3'syfsf] ;DaGw c;DaGwsf] cj:yf ljj/OfnfO{ dl;gf];Fu k|i6 x'g tnsf] nflnsfnfO{ x]/f)+ — n3'syfsf] cGo ljwfk|ljwf;Fu ;DaGw÷c;DaGwsf] cj:yf ljj/Of

ljwf	k ljwf	;DaGw÷ c;DaGw	;DaGw l:ylt	;DaGw tÇEj	c;DaGw tÇEj -k[ys\ klf_	k i6Ls/Of
cfVofg	pkGof;	;DalGwt	lgs6	cfVofg ljwfs} k ljwf ePsfn] syf / pkGof;sf tÇEjxç	cfsf/k sf/ 7'nf] ePsfn] tÇEjut pkof]usf] dfqf syf / n3'syfsf t'ngfdf a9L /xg]	—
	syf	;DalGwt	lgs6td	n3'syfsf klg tÇEj x'g\ .	demf}nf] cfsf/k sf/ x'gfn] tÇEjut k of]usf] dfqf n3'syfsf t'ngfdf a9L g} x'g]	—
sljtf	d'Qms	cf+lzs ;DalGwt	k j[lQhGo; lgs6tf	;+lIfKttf / rf]l6nf]kg	n3'syf cfVofgsf] k ljwf / d'Qms sljtf ljwfsf] k ljwf xf] .	ljwfut cGt3'{ng x'Fbf eg] n3'syfdf

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	uLt	cf+lzs ;DalGwt	k j[IQhGo lgs6tf	no tŒj b'a)df /xG5 - uLtdf efjgfTds no x'G5 eg] n3'syfdf ljr/sf] no x'G5 . _	cfsf/k sf/, k :t'tLs/Of	ljwf, sfJofTds k j[IQsf] lgs6tf emNsG5 .
	km'6s/ sljtf	c;DalGwt	—	—	cfsf/k sf/, k :t'tLs/Of	ljwf,
	v08sfJo	c;DalGwt	—	—	cfsf/k sf/, k :t'tLs/Of	ljwf,
	dxfsfJo	c;DalGwt	—	—	cfsf/k sf/, k :t'tLs/Of	ljwf,
gf6s	Psfª\SL	c;DalGwt	—	—	;+jfbsf] k of]u Ps} lsl;dn] gx'g', ljr/sf] cfsf/k sf/, k :t'tLs/Of	n3'syf;Fu gf6\oljwfsf] ljwfut cGt3'{ng x'Fbf ;DafbfTds k j[IQe]l6G5 .
	k"Offª\SL	c;DalGwt	—	—		
lgaGw cfTdk/s / j:t'k/s_	—	c;DalGwt	—	—	lgaGw lgtfGt j}rfl/stf] ljr/sf] t/ n3'syfsf] d"n tŒj j}rfl/stf] xf]Og .	n3'syf;Fu lgaGw cGt3'{ng x'Fbf lgaGw;Fu n3'syfsf] k j[IQhGo cf+lzs lgs6tf eg] emNsG5 .
r'6\lsnf	nf]s;flxTosf] xf:oJoª\UofTds k ljwf	cf+lzs ;DalGwt	k j[IQhGo lgs6tf	rf]l6nf] cleJolQm	n3'syf uDeL/ /rgf] xf] eg] r'6\lsnf nf]s 76\of}nL	—

dflysf] tflnsfaf6 lgDglnlvt s'/fxç v'Ng cfpF5g\ –

-!_ pkGof; / syf;Fu n3'syfsf] ;DaGw qmdzM lgs6 / lgs6td 5 . tLg j6} k|ljwdf k|of]u x'g] pks/Ofxç ;dfg g} x'g\ t/ lrgsf] pkof]udf eg] dfqfTds çkdf sda];L 5 .

-@_ sljtfsf d'Qms, uLt, km'6s/ sljtf, v08sfJo, dxfsfJo h:tf k|ljwf 5g\ . n3'syfn] sljtfsf d'Qms / uLt;Fu cf+lzs ;DaGw /fv5 . cGo k|ljwf;Fu eg] o;sf] slQ klg ;DaGw 5}g . sljtTds z}nLnfo{ eg] n3'syfdf cGt3'{ng ug{ ;lsG5 . o;n] n3'syfsf] çkfsif{0fnfo{ a[l4 ug{ ;3fpF5 .

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-#_ Psfª\sl / k"Off{ª\sl u/L gf6ssf b'O{ e]b 5g\ . n3'syf;Fu oL b'O{ k|ljwfsf] s'g} ;DaGw b]lvb}g . t/ gf6\ofTds z}nLnFO{ eg] n3'syfdf pkof]u ug{ ;lsG5 . pkof]usf] tl/sf eg] km/s 5 . gf6\ofTds z}nLsf] pkof]uaf6 n3'syfn] yk k|efjsfl/tf kfpF5 .

-\$_ lgaGw j}rfl/s ljwf xf] t/ n3'syf Tof] xf]Og . o;}n] oL b'O{ aLr ;DaGw b]lvFb}g . obfsbf n3'syfdf lgaGwfTds z}nLsf] k|r"/ k|j]z x'Fbf To;n] n3'syfsf] cfVofgtœjnfO{ eg] lflt k'¥ofPsf] x'G5 .

-%_ r'6\lsnf nf]s;flxTosf] Pp6f k|ljwf xf] . o;df rf]l6nf] cleJolQm x'G5 . n3'syfn] klg rf]l6nf] cleJolQmsf] dfu ug]{ x'gfn] n3'syf / r'6\lsnf eg]sf bfh'efO g} x'g\ ls eGg] e|d pTkGg x'G5 t/ of] e|daf6 n3'syf n]vsxç d'Qm x'g ;Sg'k5{ .

lgisif{ g]kfnL ;flxTodf n3'syfsf] cf^g} :yfg lgdf{Of eO;s]sf] 5 . cfVofg ljwfsf] ;zQm k|ljwfsf çkdf ;flxTodf n3'syfsf] JoflKt 5 . of] k|of]usf] r/Ofaf6 plSnP/ k|ljwfsf r/Ofdf k'lu;s]sf] 5 . of] ;flxTosf cGo ljwf / k|ljwfxçeGbf rf]l6nf] ljwfsf çkdf ljsl;t eO/x]sf] 5 . n]vg, k|sfzg, k|;f/Of, k7g, ljZn]ifOf cflbdf o;sf] bfo/f km/fs x'Fb} uPsf] 5 . o;sf n]vgdf n]vsxçn] gofF gofF z}nL / afGsLxç leq\ofO/x]sf 5g\ . k|sfzgd n3'syfsf] kx'Fr a9\b]f] 5 . s'g} ljwf;Fu glhlsP/ / s'g};Fu 6fl9P/ of] cfÇgf] ultdf lg/Gt/ ljsf;sf] l;+9L plSn/x]sf] 5 eGbf s'g} cTo'lQm x'g] 5}g .

;Gbe{ ;"rL

cof{n, nldOf -@)&#_ , ljwfut s;Ldf n3'syf, zxLb :d[lt hg{n -%÷@_ , k[= &*–!)) .

k|wfg, s[iOfrGb| l;+x -@)%@_ , g]kfnL pkGof; / pkGof;sf/, nlntk'/ M ;femf k|sfzg .

uf}td, nldOfk|;fb -@)&@_ , n3'syfsf] /rgfljwfg, sf7df8f}+ M n3'syf ;dfh .

lgzfGt/ -@)!(_ , n3'syf M /rgfljwfg cf}/ cfnf]rgf s] k|ltdfg, n3'syf snz cª\s #, k[= @* .

k'is/Off, 8f= ;tLz/fh -@)!(_ , lxGbL n3'syf M ctLt Pj+ ljsf;, n3'syf snz, cª\s #, k[= @!% .

zdf{, df]xg/fh -@)&* _ , dfnf]rgfsf gofF sf]Of, sf7df8f}F M cf]l/PG6n klAns];g xfp; .

>]i7, k|f=8f= bof/fd -@)&* _ , g]kfnL n3'syf / syfsf/xç, sdnfbL sf7df8f}F M g]kfn k|1fk|liti7fg .

Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOfsf] ;}4flGts cjwf/Off, k|lqmf / k|of]u

8f= s]zj e';fn pkk|fWofks, g]kfnL efiff lzlff ljefu, lzlffzf:q s]Gb|Lo ljefu, lq= lj= sLlt{k'/

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n]v;/

k|:t't n]v k|fof]lus efi]l]1fgsf ljleGg zfvfxçdWo]sf] Pp6f dxœjk"Of{ zfvf Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f;Fu ;DalGwt /x]sf] 5 . o; n]vdf Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf] ;}4f]Gts cjwf/0ff, cfjZostf / k|of]uaf/) rrf{ ul/Psf] 5 . j:t'tM Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf] ;}4f]Gts rrf{ ug'{, Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf] k|lqmf / k|of]usf] JofVof lj]rg ug'{ k|:t't n]vsf d'Vo p2]Zosf çkdf /x]sf 5g\ . k|:t't n]v tof/Lsf qmddf u'0ffTds cWoog lj]wsf] cjnDag ul/Psf] 5 . o; qmddf k':tsfnoLo cWoog lj]wsf] k|of]u ul/Psf] 5 . o; n]vsf nflu cfjZos s'/fxç g]kfnL, lxGbL tyf cª\ul]hL ;}4f]Gts ;fdu|Lxçsf] cWoogaf6 k|fKt ul/Psf] 5 . To;/L k|fKt tYosf] k|:t'tsf nflu JofVofTds tyf ljZn]if0ffTds lj]wsf] pkof]u ul/Psf] 5 . o; cWoogsf cfwf/df Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f b'O{ jf b'O{eGbf a9L efi]fxçsf aLrsf] t'ngfTds cWoogdf cfwf/t l;4f]Gtsf çkdf /x]sf], o;;DaGwL cjwf/0ffsf] lj]sf; ;g\ !(%) sf] bzskl5 ePsf], o;df cfwf/t eO{ ul/g] cWoogdf ;fdu|Lsf] ;ª\sng, ;fdu|Lsf] ;Tofkg, ;fdu|Lsf] JofVof ljZn]if0f / lgisif{0fh:tf k|lqmf Pjd\ k4ltxçsf] k|of]u ul/g]nufotsf lgisif{xç lgsflnPsf] 5 . k|:t't n]v Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf af/]df hfgsf/L lng rfxg] lz]fs, ljBfyL{, lh1f;' Pjd\ ;DalGwt ;a]sf nflu pkof]uL x'g] ck|lff ul/Psf] 5 .

d'Vo zAbfjnL M Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f, Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf] l;4f]Gt, Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf k|lqmf, Jolt/]sL

ljZn]if0fsf k4lt, Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf] cEof;

cWoogsf] k[i7e"ld

b'O{ jf ;f]eGbf a9L efi]fxçsf aLrdf kfOg] ;+/rgfTds ;dfgtf / c;dfgtfsf] cWoog ljZn]if0f ug{} k|fof]lus efi]l]1fgsf] zfvfnfO{ Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f elgG5 . Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fdf PseGbf a9L efi]fxçdf /x]sf Joj:yf, pkJoj:yf Pjd\ ljz]iftfxçsf] t'ngfTds cWoog ul/G5 . Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf] cjwf/0ff efi]l]sfOsf] Jojxf/jfbL l;4f]Gt;Fu ;DalGwt /x]sf] 5 -uf}td, @)^!M*&_ . o;df efi] efi]ffsf aLrsf] ;x;DaGw klxNofpg] / ;dfgtfeGbf c;dfgtfsf] cWoogdf hf]8 lbOg] x'Fbf o;sf] k|s[lT t'ngfTds,

;x;DaGwTds tyf Jolt/]sL lsl;dsf] x'G5 . Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f Psflws efi]ffsf] cWoog;Fu ;DalGwt /x]sfn] o;sf dfWodaf6 efi]ffsf ;fj{ef}d ljz]iftfxç klxrfGg ;lsG5 . of] efi] l;sfOsf] Jojxf/jfbL l;4f]Gt;Fu ;DalGwt ljifo xf], To;]n] o;sf] ;DaGw z]lfl0fs k|of]hg;Fu /x]sf] 5 . z]lfl0fs ;Gbe{df k|foM b'O{ j6f efi]ffsf] t'ngf ul/G5 h;dWo] Pp6f efi]f ljBfyL{sf] dft[efi]ff -;|f]t efi]ff_ x'G5 eg] csf{} rflx f nlo efi]ff -bf];|f] efi]ff_ . efi]ff lzlf0fdf ljBfyL{sf] dft[efi]ff / k7gkf7gsf] efi]ff Pp6] x'Fbf efi]ff l;sfO h]hlt ;xh / pkn]Awd"ns x'G5 leGg x'Fbf Tolt ;xh / pkn]Awd"ns x'Fb]g cyf{t\ nlo efi]ffsf] ;+/rgf ;|f]t efi]ffsf] ;+/rgf;Fu ldNbf]h'Nbf] eP l;sfO ;/n tl/sfn] l56f] / geP sl7g tl/sfn] l9nf] x'g] cj:yf b]vfk]b{5 . o;f] x'g'sf k5fl8 k|To]s efi]ffsf] ;+/rgfTds ;jçkn] efi]ff;fk]lf e"l]dsf lgjf{x u/]sf] x'G5 . Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fdf dft[efi]ff / nlo efi]ffsf aLrsf] ;+/rgfTds ;dtf / leGgtfsf] ;"ld cWoog ul/g] ePsf]n] o;af6 efi]ffljz]ifsf ldNbf-cl]dNbf clenlf0faf/] hfgsf/L k|fKt x'G5 . efi]ff lzlf0fsf qmddf ;|f]t / nlo efi]ffsf aLr /x]sf c;dfgtfxçnfO{ ljz]if Wofg lbO{ lzlf0f ubf{ l;sfO lzlf0f

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a9L k|efjsf/L aGg k'Ub5 . o;sf nflu Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOf ljz]iffwf/ aGb5 . k|:t't n]vdf Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOf;Da4 log} ljlw klfxçsf} rrf{ kl/rrf{ ul/Psf} 5 .

cWoog ljlw / k|lqmof

k|:t't n]v u'OffTds cg';Gwfgdf cfwf/t /x]sf} 5 . o;sf nflu cfjZos ;fdu|Lxçsf} ;ª\sng k':tsfnoLo ljlwsf dfWodaf6 ul/Psf} 5 . o; qmddf Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOfsf af/]df rrf{ ul/Psf g}kfnL, lxGbL tyf cª\u|]hL ;}4flGts ;fdu|Lxçsf} cWoog ul/Psf} 5 / cfjZos s'/fxçsf} u|xOf ul/Psf} 5 . k|:t't n]vdf d"ntM låtLos ;|f]tsf ;fdu|Lxçsf} pkof]u ul/Psf} 5 . ;fy} lj1xçsf /fo Pjd\ ;'emfjxçnfO{ k|fylds ;|f]tsf çkdf pkof]u ul/Psf} 5 . o;df k|fKt tYoxçnfO{ JofVofTds tyf ljZn]ifOfTds çkdf k|:t't ul/Psf} 5 . Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOfsf} kl/ro / kl/efiff

b'O{ jf ;f]eGb a9L efiiffsf} t'ngfTds cWoog;Fu Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOf ;DalGwt /x]sf} 5 . o;nfO{ Jolt/]sL efiiffj1fg jf Jolt/]sL cWoog klG elgPsf} kFOG5 -clwsf/L, @)^%M!@&_ . Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOfdf efiiffxçsf} cWoog ljZn]ifOf ubf{ ljleGg efiiffj}1flgs tx -jOff{Tds, çkftds, jfSofTds, zAbe08f/ut, z}nLut cflb_ nfO{ cfwf/ agfOG5 . o; qmddf efiiff efiiffsf aLrsf} cGt;{DaGw jf c;DaGwsf} cWoog ul/G5 . cGt;{DaGw cWoog ubf{ Jolt/]sL Wjlg jf jOf{sf} ljZn]ifOf, çkftds ;çksf} ljz]iftf ljZn]ifOf, çksf} Jofs/Iofs cy{ ljZn]ifOf, kbqmd ljZn]ifOf, çksf} ;+/rgfTds ljZn]ifOf tyf zflAbs ;DaGwsf} ljZn]ifOf ul/G5 eg] c;DaGwsf} cWoog ubf{ çkftlÇjs k|OffnLsf} t'ngfTds ljZn]ifOf, zflAbs cy{sf} t'ngfTds ljZn]ifOf, çkftGt/OffTds ;dfgtfsf} ljZn]ifOf tyf bf];|f] efiiff l;sfOsf} afwf ljZn]ifOf ul/G5 . efiifs kl/jf/ lgwf{/Ofsf nflu efiiffxçsf aLrsf} cGt;{DaGw kQf nufpg' / bf];|f] efiiffsf} cfh{gdf b}vfkG{ } Jojwfgsf} cWoog ug{' Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOfsf d"ne"t b'O{ p2}Zo x'g\ tyflk of} klxnf]df eGb bf];|f] p2}Zodf a9L s]lGb|t b}vfk5{ . o; cg';f/ l;sfOsf qmddf olb ljBfyL{n} Ps} lsl;dsf uNtL af/Daf/ bf]xf]¥ofpF5 eg] To;df dft[efiiffsf} k|efj dfGg'kb{5 / To;sf} klxrfg u/L lzlfOf ug{'kb{5 . ljBfyL{n} klxnf} efiiffsf} lgod bf];|f] efiiffdf k|of]u ubf{ o:tf} l:ylt pTkGg x'G5 . Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOfsf} ;}4flGts cfwf/ efiiffsf} lzlfOfsf nflu pkof]uL ;flat ePsf} 5 -nD;fn, ld=g=_ . bf];|f] jf ljb}zL efiiff l;sfOsf qmddf b]lvG} o; lsl;dsf ;d:ofxçsf} ;dfwfgfy{ Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOf lgs} pkof]uL /x]sf} 5 .

Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOfsf cfwf/df bf];|f] jf nlo efiiff l;sfOsf ;d:ofsf} JofVof ljj]rg Pjd\ k"jf{g'dfg ug{ klG ;lsG5 . o; cg';f/ ;|f]t efiiff / nlo efiiffsf aLr ;+/rgfTds Psçktf x'Fbf ;|f]t efiiffdf l;]sf Joj:yfsf} :yfgfGt/Of x'G5 / l;sfOdf sl7gfO sd x'G5 eg] ;+/rgfTds j]ljWo x'Fbf l;sfO ;d:ofd"ns aGg k'Ub5 . o:tf} l:ylnfO{ b[li6ut u/L l;sf?nfO{ bf];|f] efiiff l;Sg, l;sfpg / pQm efiiffdf 1fg k|fKt ug{, u/fpg ;xh agfpg} clek|fon} ;f]xL cg'çksf kf7\o;fdu|L, kf7\oqmd, lzlfOf ljlw cflb to ul/Psf} kFOG5 . o; ;Gbe{df klG Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOfsf} pNn]Vo e"ldsf b]lvG5 .

bf];|f] efiiff l;sfOsf ;d:of ;dfwfgfy{ lsl;t o; l;4fGtsf} k[i7e"ldsf çkdf !(cf)+ ztJbLsf} t'ngfTds efiiffj}1flgs cWoog /x]sf} dflgG5 . nfld5fg, -@)^^_ sf cg';f/ Jolt/]sL efiiffj1fg Jolt/]sL

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ljZn]if0fsf] kof{osf çkdf ljsf; ePsf] dflgG5 . efiffj1fgsf ;Gbe{df o; ;DaGwL cjwf/OffnfO{ ;j{k|yd xf]km{ -;g\ !(\$%_ n) / k|fof]lus efiffj1fgsf lf]qdf bf];|f] ljZjo'4kl5 cd]l/sL efiffj}1flgs rfN; ;L= k|mfOh -;g\ !(\$%_ n) k|j]z u/fPsf] kfOG5 . k|mfOhn] l;sf?sf] dft[efiff;Fu ;dfg txdf t'ngf u/L tof/ kfl/Psf ;fdu|Lxç efiff lzif0fdf a9L k|efjsf/L x'g ;S5g\ eGg] cjwf/Off /fv];Fu} o;af/] cGo ljåfg\ xçn] rf;f] lbPsf] b]lvG5 . Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf lf]qdf k|mfOhkl5 a]lG/v -;g\ !(%#_ / /a6{ Nof8f] -;g\ !(%&_ sf] pNn]v e"ldsf /x]sf]

5 . Nof8f]sf] lnª\Ujl:6S; cqmf]; sNr/ (Linguistics across culture) gfds k':ts o; ;DaGwdf lgs} dxÇEjk"Of{ dflgG5 . ;g\ !(% / ^) sf] bzsd f lgs} k|l;l4 sdfPsf] of] l;4fGt ;g\ !(&) sf] bzskl5 eg] qmdzM x|f;f]Gd'v Pjd\ lzlyn x'Fb] uPsf] 5 . efiff;sfOsf qmddf dft[efiffsf cnfj] cGo k|efjs tÇEjxç -jftfj/Of, clek|]/Off, cg'ej, cEof; cflb_ sf sf/Of klg sl7gfO k}bf x'g] wf/Off ljsl;t ePkl5 o;sf] ;j4fGts cfwf/ sdhf]/ x'g k'u]sf] xf] .

Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f;Fu ;DalGwt s]xL kl/efiffxç lgDgfg';f/ /x]sf 5g\ M

- æJolt/]sL ljZn]if0fn] dft[efiff / cGo efiffdf ljBdfg e]bxçsf] cWoog k|:t't ub{5 .Æ - /]8\8L
- æjt{dfgdf /x]sf b'O{ jf clws eflifs Joj:yfsf] t'ngfnfO{ Jolt/]sL efiffj1fg eg]/ lrlgG5 . - adf{ / cGo
- æb'O{ jf a9L efiffxçsf] eflifs Joj:yfsf] Jojl:yt t'ngf Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f xf] h;nfO{ Jolt/]sL efiffj1fg klg elgG5 .Æ - b OG;fOSnf]k]l8of ckm Nofª\Uj]h PG8 lnª\Ujl:6S;
- æJolt/]sL cWoogdf b'O{ jf b'O{eGbf a9L efiffsf aLr ljleGg :t/df kfOg] ;dfgtf / ljifdtfnfO{ kQf nufOG5 .Æ - /jLGb|gfy >Ljf:tj
- æJolt/]sL ljZn]if0fn] b'O{ jf ;f]eGbf a9L efiffxçsf aLr ;+/rgfTds Psçktf tyf leGgtfxçsf] j0f{g ub{5 .Æ - OG;fOSnf]k]l8s l8S:g/L ckm cKnfO8 lnª\Ujl:6S;
- æb'O{ efiffxçsf] eflifs Joj:yfsf] t'ngf Jolt/]sL efiffj1fg xf] .Æ - nªDofg l8S:g/L ckm cKnfO8 lnª\Ujl:6S;

plNnlvt kl/efiffxçsf cfwf/df klg Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fnfO{ b'O{ jf ;f]eGbf a9L efiffxçsf aLr ;+/rgfTds Psçktf / kfy{Sosf] cWoog ug{] l;4fGtsf çkdf cYof{pg ;lsG5 .

Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf] k|lqmof

Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f efiffxçdf kfOg] ;dfgtf / c;dfgtfsf] cGj]if0f;Fu ;DalGwt ljifo xf] . o;df Psflws efiffsf] cWoog ljZn]if0f Pjd\ t'ngf ul/G5 . o; qmddf ;DalGwt efiffsf ;+/rgfTds klfsf] ;dtf / ljifdtfsf] cWoog ug{] sfd x'G5 . uf}td -@)^!_ sf cg';f/ Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fdf ;fdu|L ;ª\sng, ljZn]if0f / lgisif{h:tf k|lqmofsf] cjnDag ug{ ;lsG5 . ;du|tM o;sf nflu lgDgfg';f/sf] k|lqmof cjnDag ug{' o'lQmo'Qm x'G5 M

-s_ ;fdu|L ;ª\sng

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Jolt/]sL ljZn]ifOf k|lqmofsf] klxnf] r/Of ;fdu|L ;a\sng xf] . o;sf nflu cWo]tfn] ;j{k|yd efiffsf jOff{Tds, çkfTds, jfSofTds, zAbe08f/ut jf z}nLut s'g txsf] Jolt/]sL cWoog ug{ } xf] ;f]xL cg';f/ ;|f]t / nlo efiffsf ;dfg :t/sf ;fdu|Lsf] ;a\sng ug{'kb{5 . efiffsf] df}lvs / lnlt ;|f]t tyf cWo]tf :jod\s] cGtb[{}i6 pkof]u u/L cfjZostf cg';f/ ;fdu|L ;a\sng ug{ ;lsG5 . df}lvs ;|f]taf6 ;fdu|L ;a\sng ubf{ cfjZostf';f/ ;"rssf] 5gf]6, k|ZgfjnL lgdf{0f, 5nkmn, cGtj{tf{ tyf lnlt ;|f]taf6 ;fdu|L ;a\sng ubf{ pko'Qm n]Vo ;fdu|Lsf] 5gf]6 ug{'kb{5 .

-v_ ;fdu|Lsf] ;Tofkg

;a\sInt ;fdu|Lsf] ;Totf k|dfloft ug{ } sfo{nfO{ ;fdu|Lsf] ;Tofkg elgG5 . o; cGtu{t cWo]tf jf ljZn]ifsn] ;a\sng u/]sf ;fdu|LxçnfO{ ;Tofkg ug{ } sfo{ x'G5 . cWo]tfn] ;a\sng u/]sf ;fdu|Lxç ;xL / k|fdfl0fs xf]pmg\ eGgsf nflu ;DalGwt efiffsf 1ftf, ljåfg tyf ljz]if1xçaf6 ?h' u/fpg' cfjZos x'G5 .

-u_ ;fdu|Lsf] JofVof / juL{s/Of

o; cGtu{t ;Tofkg ul/Psf ;fdu|Lxçsf] cWoog u/L af]w ug{ }, c;dfgtf klxrfg ug{ }, JofVof ug{ } / ljleGg txdf juL{s/Of ug{ } sfd ul/G5 . o;af6 ;DalGwt efiffdf /x]sf Jolt/]sxçnfO{ lj]rg ug{ ;3fp k'Ub5 . JofVof lj]rgsf nflu efiffj1fgsf ;+/rgfjfbL, çkfy{k/s, Joj:yfk/s, çkGt/OfjfbL nufotsf l;4fGtxçdWo] s'g} Ps jf a9Lsf] pkof]u ug{ ;lsG5 .

-3_ t'ngfTds ljZn]ifOf

Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf] o; r/Ofdf ljleGg txdf juL{s/Of ul/Psf eflifs ;fdu|LxçnfO{ t'ngfTds çkdf ljZn]if0f ug{ } sfd x'G5 . o; qmddf ;|f]t / nlo efiffdf /x]sf ;dfgtf / c;dfgtfsf] t'ngf ubf{ } Jojl:yt çkdf JofVof-ljZn]if0f ul/G5 . o;af6 k|fKt ;dfgtfn] b'O{ efiffsf aLr ;+of]hg / c;dfgtfn] ljof]hg ug{ } sfo{ ubf{5 . o;df efiffxçsf aLrdf kfOg] leGgtf, To;sf] sf/Of, ;çk jf k|s[ltsf] cWoogdf ljz]if hf]8 lbOG5 .

-a_ lgisif{0f

of] Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f k|lqmofsf] clGtd r/Of xf] . o; r/Ofdf t'ngfTds ljZn]if0faf6 k|fKt tYonfO{ cfwf/ agfP/ lgisif{ k|:t't ul/G5 . o; qmddf ;|f]t / nlo efiffsf aLrsf] ;dfgtf, c;dfgtf, c;dfgtfsf cfwf/df Jolt/]s L lgods] lgwf/{ 0f, ;Defljt ql' 6sf] klxrfg Pjd \ kj" fg{ d' fg nufotsf s/' fxç lgrf8] sf çkdf cfp5F g \ .

Jol/t/]sL ljZn]if0fsf k4lt

Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f b'O{ 9a\un] x'g ;S5 M -s_ ;dtnLo -v_ pmWj{tnLo -clwsf/L, @)^%M!#@_ . Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf ;Gbe{df lgDgfg';f/sf k4ltxçsf] k|of]u ul/G5 M

-s_ ;dtnLo k4lt

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efiff! / efiff@ jf ; |f]t efiff / nlo efiffsf eflifs tŒjxç -j0f{, çk, jfSo, z}nL cflb_ sf] t'ngfTds cWoog u/L Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f ug{} k4ltnfO{ ;dtnLo k4lt elgG5 . o; k4ltdf k|foM b'O{ j6f efiffsf] dfq cWoog ul/g] ePsf]n] o;sf] lf]q cToGt ;Lldt /x]sf] b]lvG5 . efiff l;sfO lzlf0fsf b[li6n] eg] o; k|s[Its] Jolt/]sL cWoognfO{ lgs} dxŒjk"0f{ dflgG5 .

-v_ pWj{tnLo k4lt

b'O{eGbf a9L efiffxçsf eflifs tŒjxçsf] t'ngfTds cWoog u/L Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f ug{} k4ltnfO{ pWj{tnLo k4lt elgG5 . o; k4ltaf6 ;deflifs jf ljifdeflifs kl/jf/sf ljleGg efiffxçsf] k|sf/fTds cWoog ;Dej x'G5 . ;dtnLo k4ltsf t'ngfdf cIn ;}4flGts k|s[Its] dflgg] o; k4ltsf cfwf/df efiffsf ;fj{ef}d ljz]iftsf] vf]hL ug{ ;lsG5 .

Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf] cEof;fTds k|of]u

Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fdf cfwf/df b'O{ jf ;f]eGbf a9L efiffsf] t'ngfTds cWoog u/L Itgdf kfOg] ;dfgtf- c;dfgtf klxrfGg ;lsG5 . o:tf] cWoog cEof;fTds k4ltaf6 ubf{ cem a9L k|efjsf/L x'g hfG5 . nfld5fg] -@)^^_ sf cg';f/ s'g} b'O{ efiffsf aLrdf s]s:tf ;dfgtf / leGgtfxç 5g\ Itgsf] cWoogsf nflu ljBfyL{nfO{ cWof;df cu| ;f/ agfpg'kb{5 . j:t'tM cEof;fTds sfo{ ; |f]t efiff / nlo efiffsf] ls6fg ePkl5 dfq ug{' u/fpg' pko'Qm x'G5 . o;f] ubf{ efiffsf ;du| klfdf eGbf s'g} Ps jf b'O{ klfdf s]lGb|t /xg'nfO{ /fd|f] dflgG5 . o; l;nl;nfdf ljBfyL{xçnfO{ efiffsf j0ff{Tds, çlklDs, jfSofTds, zAbe08f/ut, z}nLut jf cGo txdWo] s'g}df cEof; u/fpg ;lsG5 . cEof;sf r/0fdf Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0fsf ;du| k|lqmofxçsf] cjnDag ug{' >}o:s/ x'G5 .

oxfF yfç efiff / g]kfnL efiffsf aLr Jofs/I0fs sf]l6 -gfdsf] ln^au, jrg, k'?if / cfb/ dfq_ sf cfwf/df ;+/rgfTds efiff]j1fgsf] dfGotf cg'çk Jolt/]sL ljZn]if0f ul/Psf] 5 . o;af6 yfç dft[efifL ljBfyL{n] g]kfnL efiffsf Jofs/OffTds sf]l6sf] l;sfO / k|of]udf sxfFsxf sl7gfO dx;' ; u5{g\ jf uNtL u5{g\ eGg]af/] hfgsf/L k|fKt ug{ ;lsG5 .

ln		^a u	
g]kfnL efiff		Yffç	efiff
k'ln ^a u	:qLln ^a u	k'ln ^a u	:qLln ^a u
a'jf	cfdf	afaf	8fO{
5f]/f]	5f]/L	5fjf	5fO{
kf7f]	kf7L	k7jf	kl7of
af3	al3gL	a3jf	al3lgof

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tyf]St pbfx/Of cg';f/ g]kfnL efiffdf k'ln^a\uL gfdnfO{ :qLln^a\uL gdddf kl/jt{g ubf{ leGg} zAbsf cltl/St 'O{' , 'PgL' , 'OgL' , 'gL' h:tf k|Toosf] of]u ul/G5 eg] yfç efiffdf leGg} zAbsf cltl/St 'O' , 'Oof' h:tf k|Toosf] of]u ul/G5 . o;af6 yfç efifL ljbFyL{xçn] g]kfnL efiiff] l;sfOdf k'ln^a\uL gfdnfO{ :qLln^a\uL agfpFbf sl7gfO dx;' ; ug{] jf uNtL ug{] ;Defjgf /xG5 egL k''jf{g'dfg ug{ ;lsG5

j		g	
g]kfnL efiff		yfç efiff	
Psjrg	ax'jrg	Psjrg	ax'jrg
5f]/f]	5f]/f÷5f]/fxç	5fjf	5fjfg\
5f]/L	5f]/Lxç	5fO{	5fO{g\s]
;fyL	;fyLxç	;a]/jf	;a]/jfg\

o; cg';f/ g]kfnL efiffdf Psjrg gfdnfO{ ax'jrg agfpFbf ...'cf' / 'xç' k|Toosf] of]u ul/G5 eg] yfç efiffdf 'g\s]' jf 'g\' k|Toosf] of]u ul/G5 . o;af6 yfç efifL ljbFyL{xçnfO{ g]kfnL efiiff] l;sfOdf Psjrg gfdnfO{ ax'jrgdf kl/jt{g ubf{ ;d:of cfOkg{] b]lvG5 .

k'?if					
g]kfnL efiff			yfç efiff		
k yd k'?if	låtLo k'?if	t[tLo k'?if	k yd k'?if	låtLo k'?if	t[tLo k'?if
d, xfdL	tF, ltdL, tkfOF, xh', oxfF	of], logL, pm, pgL, Tof], ltgL	d}, xd/]	6}, 6'	oL, pm

pko{'Qm pbfx/Of cg';f/ yfç efiiff] låtLo k'?ifdf 6} -tF_ / 6' -ltdL_ sf] dfq k|of]u x'g] ePsf] g]kfnLsf tF, ltdL, tkfOF, xh', oxfF h:tf leGg-leGg låtLo k'?ifsf nflu s'g} Pp6f k'?ifsf] k|of]u ug{] l:ylt b]lvG ;S5 eg] t[tLo k'?if of], logLxç k|of]u ug{'kg{] 7fpFdf logL÷logLxç / pgL, pgLxç, pxfF, pxfFçsf 7fpFdf pm÷pgLxç k|of]u ug{] ;Defjgf /xG5 .

cfb/		
cfb/fyL{	g]kfnL efiff	yfç efiff
cfb//lxt	tF 3/ hfG5g\ .	6} 3/] hfOa] .
dWod cfb/	ltdL 3/ hfG5f} .	6'F 3/ hfOaf] .
pRr cfb/	tkfOF 3/ hfg'x'G5 .	---

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pRrt/ cfb/	oxF÷xh'/ 3/ hfg'x'G5 .	---
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o;cg';f/ yfçefifL lJBfyL{xçn} g]kfnL efiffsf] l;sfOdf pRr / pRrt/ cfb/ k|of]udf sl7gfO dx;'; ug{} tyf tt\ lf]qdf uNtL ug{} -ltdL 3/ hfg'x'G5, tkfOF 3/ hfG5f)+ cflb_ ;Defjgf b]lvG5 .

o;sf cnfjf yfç efifL lJBfyL{xçn} g]kfnL efiffsf] l]elQm k|of]u -u'?n] cf1f eof], p;af6 dnfO{ lk6\of] cflb_ , cs/Of k|of]u -ltdL 3'Dg ghfGYof}, xfdLn] sfd g}u/) cflb_ tyf sf / klfsf] k|of]u - pgn] eft vfof], tF eft vfO/x]sf lyO; cflb_ df klq q'l6 ug{} ;Defjgf /xG5 . efj / jfRosf ;Gbe{df k|foM b'a} efiffsf l]z]iftf ldNg] x'Fbf logsf] l;sfO / k|of]udf sl7gfO / q'l6 ug{} ;Defjgf eg] cToGt sd /xG5 .

o;k|sf/ efiff lzlf0fsf qmddf lzlfns] yfç efifL lJBfyL{xçn} g]kfnL efiffsf] l;sfOdf sl7gfO dx;'; ug{} jf uNtL ug{} pko{'Qm jf cGo lf]qsf af/]df hfgsf/L k|fkt u/L lzlf0f ubf{ l;sfO pknIAw ck]lffs[t a9]/ hfg] x'G5 . ;fy} cGoefifL lJBfyL{xçnfO{ g]kfnL efiff l;sfpFbf klq ;|f]t efiff / nlo efiffsf aLr /x]sf cldNbf clenlf0fxçdf Wofg lbP/ l;sfO lzlf0f sfos{ nfk ;~rfng ugk'{ b5{ h;af6 nllft p2Z} o kf|Kt ug { d2t kU' b5 . lgisif{

;du|tM Jolt/]sL l]Zn]if0f k|fof]lus efiffj1fgsf] zfvfsf çkdf /x]sf] kFOG5 . o;sf] l]sf; ;g\ !(% sf] bzskl5 ePsf] b]lvG5 . o;n] lglZrt ;}4f]Gts dfGotfsf cfwf/df b'O{ jf b'O{eGbf a9L efiffsf aLrsf] t'ngfTds cWoognfO{ b;f{pFb5 . o;df s'g} klq efiffxçsf aLrsf] t'ngfTds cWoog l]Zn]if0f ubf{ ;fdu|Lsf] ;ç\ng, ;fdu|Lsf] ;Tofkg, ;fdu|Lsf] JofVof, ;fdu|Lsf] l]Zn]if0f / lgisif{0fh:tf k|lqomfxçsf] pkof]u ug{} ul/G5 . o; l;4fGtdf ;dtnLo / pWj{tnLo u/L b'O{ j6f k4ltsf] ;d]t k|of]u ul/G5 . oLdWo] ;dtnLo k4ltdf s'g} b'O{ efiff jf ;|f]t efiff / nlo efiffsf aLrsf] c;dfgtfsf] cWoog ul/G5 eg] pWj{tnLo k4ltdf b'O{eGbf a9L efiffxçsf l]leGg klfsf] t'ngfTds cWoog l]Zn]if0f ul/G5 . efiffxçsf aLrsf] ;dfgtf / leGgtfsf] t'ngfTds cWoogaf6 eflifs ;DaGw, Oltxf;, ;dfgtf, leGgtfaf/] hfgsf/L k|fkt x'g'sf ;fy} l;sfO ;xhLs/Of Pjd\ l;sfO ;d:of ;dfwfgsf nflu klq oy]i6 d2t k'Ug] b]lvG5 .

;Gbe{"rL

clwsf/L, x]dfª\ u/fh -@)%^_ , ;fdlhs / k|fof]lus efiffj1fg, sf7df8f)+M /Tg k':ts e08f/ . uf}td, /fdk|;fb -@)^!_, k|fof]lus efiffj1fgsf k|d'v cfofd, sf7df8f)+M bLlffGt k':ts e08f/ .

ltjf/L, ef]nfgfy -;g\ !(*%_ , cfw'lgs efiffj1fg , lbNnLM lnk k|sfzg . låj]bL, slknb]j -;g\ @))^!_, efiffj1fg Pjd\ efiffzf:q, jf/f0f;LM l]Zj]lBfno k|sfzg . nD;fn, /fdrGb| / cGo -ld= g=_

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k|fof]lus efiiflj1fg, sf7df8f)+M e'F8Lk'/f0f k|sfzg . nfld5fg], ofbjk|sfz -@)^^_ ,;fdfGo /
k|fof]lus efiiflj1fg, sf7df8f)+M ljBfyL{ k':ts e08f/ . Inof]G;, hf]g -;g\ @))#_ ,Nofª\Uj]h
PG8 lnª\|Ujl:6S; Pg OG6«f]8S;g, n08gM SoflDa|h o'lgeI;{6L k|]; . n]ljG;g, ;L= :6]kmg -
;g\ @)!_ , k|UdfI6S; n08gM SoflDa|h o'lgeI;{6L k|]; . zdf{, pdfgfy / cGo -;g\ @)!_ ,
cKnfO8 lnª\|Ujl:6S;, sf7df8f)+M ;gnfO6 klAns];g .

>Ljf:tj, /jLGb|gfy -;g\ @)))_ , cg'k|o'Qm efiiflj1fg M l;4fGt Pjd\ k|of]u, lbNnLM /fwfs[i0f
k|sfzg .